

**EXPLORING THE DRIVERS OF COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN WILDLIFE
CONSERVATION IN THE GREATER SERONGA AREA OF THE OKAVANGO
DELTA, BOTSWANA**

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Abstract

Participation of local communities in conservation begins with addressing challenges affecting livelihoods of those living in proximity to natural resources under conservation. Livelihoods are usually affected by management decisions and initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable coexistence of humans and wildlife. Poor community participation in conservation initiatives raises concern as the success of those initiatives is predicated on local communities' perception and support. Informed by the motivation-opportunity-ability (MOA) model of community participation and the Social-ecological systems (SES) framework, this thesis analysed the drivers of community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga Area of the Okavango Delta, Botswana. Specific objectives were (a) to assess socio-cultural factors influencing local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives, (b) to analyse the influence of formal management strategies on local community participation in wildlife conservation, and (c) to assess the influence of household economic trade-offs on local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives.

A cross-sectional passive-analytical mixed-methods approach was used. Household survey was used to collect primary data from 248 household heads selected by simple random sampling from the villages of Seronga, Gunotsoga, Eretsha, Beetsha and Gudigwa. Data were analysed using quantitative techniques including Spearman's rho correlation coefficient (ρ) test and Pearson Chi-Square (χ^2) test. Qualitative techniques included thematic analysis and key-word-in-context. This thesis demonstrated that the ability of local communities in the Greater Seronga Area to participate in management of wildlife was influenced by socio-cultural attributes, including lack of knowledge, notable skills, and awareness. There was low positive correlation ($\rho= 0.474$) between

available platforms of stakeholder engagement and community participation. Furthermore, wildlife management processes were largely centred around the central government.

Local communities living alongside wildlife in the Greater Seronga Area suffered costs such as crop damages and livestock predation by wildlife. Compared to benefits gained, results indicated that 80% of respondents did not benefit economically from wildlife conservation initiatives. The Chi-square test ($\chi^2=53.850$; p-value of 0.000) yielded a significant association between benefits and participation in wildlife management. Where there were more costs with less benefits, local communities were less inclined to participate in the conservation even if they had the ability and opportunity to do so. Local community participation in wildlife conservation in the Greater Seronga Area was largely consultative due to detrimental drivers of community participation (such as knowledge, notable skills, and awareness; absence of inclusive wildlife management platforms; and lack of motivation) that are necessary to enable local communities to participate as demonstrated in this thesis. It is vital for government to develop and support implementation of area-specific and interactive wildlife management strategies and processes, that complement the setting up of community-based organisations with strong community empowerment, capacity building and distribution of benefits.

Keywords: Community participation, conservation initiatives, natural resources management, Okavango Delta, wildlife

Dedication

Abraham Lincoln once said, “All that I am or ever hope to be, I owe to my mother”. I dedicated this thesis to my mother, Ms Bapaladzi Kgotlaeole, such a strong, loving, protective, and supportive woman.

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Foremost, I thank God for the gift of life, he is almighty.

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Disclaimer

This document is a result of my investigation and findings undertaken at Okavango Research Institute (ORI), University of Botswana for the MPhil Programme. The work in this thesis was completed at the University of Botswana between June 2018 and June 2021. It is original work except where due references are made, and it has never been submitted to any University for the award of any academic degree or diploma. All views and opinions expressed herein remain the sole responsibility of the author, and do not necessarily represent those of the institute.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CAMPFIRE	Communal Area Management Programme for Indigenous Resources
CBNRM	Community Based Natural Resource Management
CBO	Community Based Organisation
CBPP	Contagious Bovine Pleuropneumonia
CBT	Community Based Tourism
FMD	Foot and Mouth Disease
JFM	Joint Forest Management
KRST	Khama Rhino Sanctuary Trust
MOA	Motivation, Opportunity, and Ability
MPA	Marine Protected Area
NGO	Non – Governmental Organisation
OCT	Okavango Community Trust
PA	Protected Area
PAMB	Protected Area Management Board
SES	Social – Ecological Systems
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization
VDC	Village Development Committee
WHS	World Heritage Site

1 **CHAPTER 1**

2 **INTRODUCTION**

3 **1.1 Background**

4 Participation of local communities in conservation begins with addressing challenges affecting
5 livelihoods of those living in proximity to natural resources under conservation (Hoon, 2014).

6 Conservation initiatives are usually implemented to mitigate shocks experienced by local
7 communities due to natural threats and community activities threatening natural resources in their
8 vicinity (Chen, Yi, Campos-Arceiz, Chen, & Webb, 2013; Woodroffe, Thirgood, & Rabinowitz,

9 2005). Success of those conservation initiatives is often predicated on local communities’
10 perception and level of support towards those initiatives. Subsequently the impacts, and results

11 expected and experienced by local communities particularly on conservation initiatives are key
12 determinants of outcomes of opinions of management and governance (Bennett & Dearden, 2014).

13 Local communities have a sense of belonging of their immediate surrounding and resources they
14 consume. The sense of belonging is attributed to social integration and association, and influence
15 individuals to participate in a broad range of social relations including social and economic
16 wellbeing which their livelihoods depend on (Cohen, Underwood, & Gottlieb, 2000).

17
18 Dwellers in rural and underdeveloped regions are considered by Bunting et al. (2013) as more
19 vulnerable to livelihoods shocks due to dependence on depleting natural resources, growing

20 populations and minimal means of risk management or mitigation. Their vulnerability is
21 influenced by the proximity to wildlife protected areas which serve as the breeding, living and

22 survival space for predators and crop raiders which pose a threat to livelihood assets like livestock
23 and crop fields (Parker, Whittington-Jones, Bernard, & Davies-Mostert, 2014). Consequently, the

24 vulnerability increases dependency on external support from government and other institutions in
25 terms of inclusive policies and initiatives which promote realisation of natural resource value, use
26 and benefit amid costs and externalities of livestock predation and crop raiding. Lack of mitigation
27 welfares and alternative strategies towards these costs and externalities may lead to negative
28 tendencies such as retaliation (Okello, Bonham, & Hill, 2014), towards natural resources (National
29 Research Council, 2002).

30
31 In the early 1990's, many native communities around the world adopted the concept of
32 community-based natural resource management (commonly referred to as CBNRM) for both
33 human welfare development and conservation (Wesche, 1996). For example, in Ecuador, South
34 America, community-based management was found to be the most optimal way of using natural
35 resources with minimal destruction. Likewise, in the last two decades, there has been significant
36 incorporation of community-based approach policy development in the management of natural
37 resources in southern Africa (Katerere, Hill, & Moyo, 2001). Initiatives such as the Communal
38 Area Management Programme for Indigenous Resources (CAMPFIRE) in Zimbabwe has been
39 developed to safeguard communities level of use and benefit from their natural resources
40 (Mutandwa & Gadzirayi, 2007). The process recognised the importance of individuals
41 participation in decision making about their social and economic wellbeing. Across disciplines,
42 community participation is becoming more recognized as a crucial component in decision making
43 processes (Chan, 2016).

44
45 CBNRM was more appealing to international funders than other strategies due to its multi-faceted
46 nature in addressing both social and conservation issues simultaneously (Wesche, 1996; Wood,
47 1998). In Botswana, local communities are players in natural resource management, they have

48 mandatory privileges even though the central role in management of resources is played by the
49 central government (Arntzen, 2005). The notion on the CBNRM initiative in Botswana is to
50 empower rural communities living alongside protected areas to have control over use of and
51 benefit from resources (Moswete & Thapa, 2018). Since early 1990's introduction of CBNRM has
52 been associated with the decline in illegal wildlife killings in areas where CBNRM programmes
53 operate and where communities mostly engaged in safari hunting tourism. The programme yielded
54 positive ecological and socio-economic results until the introduction of the hunting ban in 2014
55 (Mbaiwa, 2018).

56
57 Participation is dependent on community perceptions about the effectiveness and quality of
58 management and governance policies, institutions, and processes (Webb, Maliao, & Siar, 2004).
59 Therefore, communities' views or perceptions towards an initiative or management strategy have
60 a direct bearing on how they will be voluntarily involved and ultimately influence the outcomes
61 of such initiatives. In Botswana, the livelihoods of communities and ecology of the Okavango
62 Delta specifically are mostly perceived as fragile due to recurrent exposure to shocks including
63 human and animal diseases such as Contagious Bovine Pleuropneumonia (CBPP), Foot and Mouth
64 Disease (FMD) and HIV (Arntzen, 2005). Most households in such areas are vulnerable to
65 livelihoods shocks and consequently poverty, despite the presence of many interventions (Bunting
66 et al., 2013). Participatory conservation approach is thus generally a legitimate and conducive way
67 of addressing conservation conflicts and increase compliance and tolerance of communities
68 towards natural resources.

69
70 It is thus important to ensure that community participation is incorporated into conservation tools
71 because the success and support of conservation initiatives is usually predicated by community's

72 perceived effectiveness and benefits, which is derived from the level of participation (Webb,
73 Maliao, & Siar 2004; Bennett & Dearden 2014). The increase in wildlife conservation initiatives
74 alongside their associated local community's livelihood challenges has attracted the attention to
75 the field. This has been coupled with studies trying to highlight and address problems that
76 resources, particularly in protected areas brings to social groups inside and around them (West et
77 al., 2006). Work in the field led to the promotion of CBNRM mainly adopted from the participatory
78 development approach over time where it is an intervention tool in conservation resulting in
79 sustainable solutions (Campbell & Vainio-Mattila, 2003). Community participation in
80 conservation as a management approach is considered to be a pertinent intervention to socio-
81 ecological problems, as it brings mutual benefit to both biodiversity and local communities
82 (Adams & Hutton, 2007; Chan et al., 2020; Noga, Kolawole, Thakadu, & Masunga, 2018).
83 Rodríguez-Izquierdo, Gavin, and Macedo-Bravo (2010) opined that local community participation
84 is critical for conservation success through community involvement, with different management
85 stages that present an opportunity for participation.

86
87 Rodríguez-Izquierdo, Gavin and Macedo-Bravo (2010) highlighted that local community
88 participation is critical for conservation success through community involvement. Involving local
89 communities as key stakeholders has potential to help locals through benefits of mitigation on
90 environmental and livelihood threats. The outcomes of conservation initiatives are primarily
91 determined by communities expected and experienced impacts and results from those initiatives
92 (Bennett & Dearden, 2014). It is important to ensure community participation is incorporated in
93 natural resources management tools to influence perceptions and expectations and thus better
94 outcomes in both management initiatives and livelihoods. Therefore, a clear understanding of

95 factors influencing communities to participate in natural resources management tools is equally
96 important.

97
98 **1.2 Statement of the problem**

99 There is a visible gap in the understanding of dynamics leading to effective community
100 participation, particularly in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Okavango Delta. As most rural
101 people in northern Botswana are farmers who are economically and socially deprived (Moepeng,
102 2013), their persistent exposure to livelihoods risks triggers a need for understanding factors
103 influencing their participation in management of natural resources and consequently their natural
104 resources use, value and benefit overtime. Households in such areas, the majority of which are
105 farmers, are more vulnerable to unforeseen consequences despite the presence of many
106 interventions (Bunting et al., 2013). The consequences come to farmers in form of losses to
107 farming activities, due to persisting human-wildlife conflict, specifically crop raiding and livestock
108 predation without enough relief and benefits to sustain their livelihoods (Karanth, Gopaldaswamy,
109 Defries, & Ballal, 2012; Kicheleri, Treue, Kajembe, Mombo, & Nielsen, 2019; McManus,
110 Dickman, Gaynor, Smuts, & Macdonald, 2015; McNutt, Stein, McNutt, & Jordan, 2017; Dilys
111 Roe, Jones, Bond, & Bhatt, 2006; Rust & Marker, 2013).

112
113 Livelihoods of communities living in proximity to protected areas are mainly affected by
114 management decisions and initiatives in promoting sustainable coexistence of humans and wildlife
115 in the ecosystem. Persistent underperformance of conservation initiatives in addressing issues
116 caused by obligatory boundaries on “human use and occupancy” (West, Igoe, & Brockington,
117 2006: pp. 252) of natural resources is thus a source of concern to governments and a challenge in
118 the attainment of conservation outcomes and development objectives. The underperformance can

119 be attributed to poor community participation in conservation initiatives or strategies which raises
120 concern in the face of a nation's efforts for sustainability of resources use and rural development.
121 There is need for contextualisation of management regimes to match local relationships and
122 institutional structures for practicality and sustainability (Lejano, Ingram, Whiteley, Torres, &
123 Agduma, 2007). There has been growing interest in research and policy development focusing on
124 natural resource management and emergence of some initiatives involving communities in
125 different regions including southern Africa (Katerere et al., 2001). In Botswana, interventions
126 which particularly focus on policy, institutions and involvement of communities in conservation
127 have been implemented over the years (Bowie, 2009). Many of the interventions including
128 CBNRM have their objectives focused on tourism development, biodiversity conservation and
129 community benefits without putting much emphasis on factors that may influence local
130 communities to participate in such.

131
132 Taking the Okavango Delta area as a case study, it is important to assess community participation
133 with regard to different driving factors as that has more impact on the initiatives results and
134 implications in livelihoods and the host environment. Different observable and cognitive socio-
135 cultural, administrative, and economic parameters have a direct impact on varying community
136 participation behaviours in conservation initiatives. On their evaluation of the wildlife
137 management decentralisation process in northern Botswana, Boggs (2000) found some factors
138 wanting and recommended that they be given attention in the future. The factors are considered to
139 be central to policy and project design such as the CBNRM policy. When making an evaluation of
140 CBNRM projects in Botswana, taking the cases of Khwai and Sankuyo CBOs, Boggs (2000: pp.
141 43) opined that "there is need to understand what makes community members satisfied and
142 motivated" for them to participate in natural resources management. Some of the key issues in the

143 evaluation that were mentioned to be in need of attention include, but not limited to, “specific
144 cultural realities” and “power dynamics” (Boggs, 2000). The limited understanding was also
145 observed elsewhere, examples being at Ghodaghodi Lake, western Nepal (Lamsal, Pant, Kumar,
146 & Atreya, 2015) and KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (Musavengane & Simatele, 2016). Thus, this
147 thesis aimed to assess the drivers of community participation in conservation strategies that
148 promotes sustainable livelihood outcomes and solutions to challenges of human-wildlife
149 coexistence in the Okavango Delta, Botswana.

150

151 Though Stone and Stone (2011) did not conclude that community based tourism (CBT) failed in
152 Botswana on their Khama Rhino Sanctuary Trust (KRST) case analysis, it was found out that
153 factors like community empowerment and information flow had a positive influence in the level
154 of participation and acceptance of a particular initiative, and thus its success. Understanding the
155 characteristics of drivers of community participation in conservation initiatives is very important
156 when planning, implementing, or evaluating an initiative or process. The implementation process
157 needs to be based on the fundamental understanding of driving principles and dynamics for proper
158 deliverables of sustainable welfare development and human-wildlife coexistence. Mbaiwa and
159 Stronza (2010) also acknowledge the importance of considering the socio-economic and
160 administrative circumstances of an initiative, that dynamics and characteristics of an initiative are
161 equally important in both its formulation and assessment.

162

163 Community participation in Apo marine protected areas (MPAs) for example, was viewed by
164 White, Vogt, and Arin (2000) as most successful, attested to by the extra fish biomass and increase
165 in socio-economic benefits for the communities. This adds to attestations that, the process of

166 community participation is fundamental in producing desired results in any given situation, and
167 lack of which creates a gap in addressing issues of sustainable conservation and development. The
168 change in the management of Apo marine was evident in the level of community engagement and
169 benefits during the establishment of Protected Area Management Board (PAMB), which is an
170 authority responsible for resource management and protection overriding MPAs. That signalled
171 the beginning of centralised management system in 1998 which led to the deterioration of
172 community engagement and subsequent loss of support and empowerment (Hind, Hiponia, &
173 Gray, 2010). This change in management has been labelled as being ignorant over important
174 variables and factors of community status, being motivation and benefits, in terms of their capacity
175 and ensuring their participation in the management (Mirasol, Mirasol, & Padua, 2013) and also a
176 drawback to community inclusive management efforts of MPAs.

177
178 The transition of Apo marine management demonstrates the importance of the need to understand
179 the dynamics of community participation variables that are vital in influencing management
180 outcomes. These factors are drivers of community participation in natural resources management,
181 and they have not been well studied which brings a gap in the understanding of dynamics leading
182 to certain level of community participation more especially in the context of Botswana.
183 Identification of most vital factors influencing the level of community participation is very
184 important for policy development as socio-economic features vary per communities' spatial-
185 temporal conditions. For oncoming initiatives, there are apparent challenges in generally applying
186 the community participation approach without considering divergent nature of sociocultural,
187 administrative, and economic factors and that can influence different levels of participation and
188 support and subsequently the success or performance of the initiatives (Tosun, 1999).

189

190 **1.3 Objectives of the study**

191 **1.3.1 General objective**

192 The general objective of the study was to explore the drivers of community participation in wildlife
193 conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga area of the Okavango Delta, Botswana.

194

195 **1.3.2 Specific objectives**

196 The specific objectives were:

197 a) To assess socio-cultural factors influencing local community participation in wildlife
198 conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga Area of the Okavango Delta,

199 b) To analyse the influence of formal management strategies on local community participation in
200 wildlife conservation in the Greater Seronga Area of the Okavango Delta, and

201 c) To assess the influence of household economic trade-offs on local community participation in
202 wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga Area of the Okavango Delta.

203 **1.4 Significance of the study**

204 Issues identified and conclusions reached in this thesis might offer guidance and recommendation
205 to development of natural resource management strategies which incorporate more participation
206 of local communities, which is a key pathway for sustainability (Chan et al., 2020). The agenda-
207 setting, formulation and implementation of conservation initiatives which needs efforts of local
208 communities as participants or stakeholders needs to be based on a deep and clear understanding
209 of possible factors that can influence communities to participate in such initiatives. This is
210 important because, community participation in resolution of issues affecting common pool
211 resources has relationship to the success or failure of management objectives of conservation and
212 development (Gari, Newton, Icely, & Delgado-Serrano, 2017; Mayoral-Phillips, 2002). Findings,
213 conclusions reached, and recommendations raised in the thesis possibly will help determine the
214 main factors influencing community participation, on policy and programme implications for
215 positive livelihoods outcomes and community development through conservation. The thesis can
216 also advice on how communities in remote areas could certainly adapt to shocks and sustainably
217 use natural resources to address their needs.

218 **1.5 Definition of terms and concepts**

219 **Ability** – is the possession of the means or skills to do something. In this study ability is the
220 personal capacities of members of the local communities to participate in wildlife
221 conservation initiatives and comprises a combination of factors such as awareness,
222 experience, knowledge, skills and accessibility to information and financial resources
223 (Hung, Sirakaya-Turk, & Ingram, 2011; Jepson, Clarke, & Ragsdell, 2013).

224
225 **Community** – is a group of people living in the same place or having a particular characteristic in
226 common. In this study, local community refers to people with common interests and
227 residing in a particular area, being the Greater Seronga Area.

228
229 **Conservation** – is the prevention of wasteful use of a resource. The preservation, protection, or
230 restoration of the natural environment and of wildlife. It involves government of resources
231 by people with rules and regulations through institutions and organisations.

232
233 **Conservation initiatives** – An initiative is a new plan or process to achieve something or solve a
234 problem. Therefore, a conservation initiative is formulated from a number of characteristics
235 required for successful organisations and have three broad categories: concerned
236 community outreach, collaborative management, and community-based conservation.

237
238 **Community participation** – is the involvement of people in a community in projects to solve
239 their own problems. In this study, community participation is defined as the engagement
240 of local communities in decision-making including the analysis of challenges and
241 problems, setting goals, creation of strategies and formulation of procedures in and for the
242 management of wildlife resources within the communities' locality.

243
244 **Household** – is all the people in a family or group who live together. A household is defined in
245 this study as a person or a group of persons, related or unrelated, who live together in the
246 same dwelling unit or compound, who make common provisions for basic needs, or who
247 pool their income for the purpose of obtaining basic needs.

248
249 **Motivation** – is a reason or reasons for acting or behaving in a particular way, is the act or process
250 of giving someone a reason for doing something. In this study, motivation is considered to
251 be the driving force behind a person’s decision-making process, as it affect the intensity
252 and direction of behaviour (Hung et al., 2011). It is assumed that community members are
253 more likely to participate when wildlife conservation initiatives become relevant on a
254 personal and household level. The presence of benefits which surpasses costs of living
255 alongside wildlife are factors reinforcing the relevance of wildlife conservation to
256 community members and are crucial in motivating them to participate.

257
258 **Opportunity** – is a time, chance or set of circumstances that makes it possible to do something.
259 In this study, opportunity is the circumstances that allow for and/or facilitate community
260 involvement in the participation process (Hung et al., 2011). Opportunity occurs when
261 conservation organisations provide a supportive framework for community participation.
262 Participation cannot occur without political opportunities or an open channel of
263 communication (Hung et al., 2011).

264
265 **Social capital** – is the networks of relationships among people who live and work in a particular
266 society, enabling that society to function effectively. It is the voluntary involvement of
267 people to pursue activities of common interest. Social capital has been referred to as a

268 resource base individuals have access to through their connection with others (van
269 Beuningen & Schmeets, 2013).

270
271 **Trade-offs** – a balance achieved between two desirable but incompatible features, a compromise.

272 In economics, a trade-off is a situation whereby making one choice means losing something
273 else, usually forgoing a benefit or opportunity.

274
275 **Wildlife** – is wild animals collectively; the native fauna (and sometimes flora) of a region.

276

277

278 **1.6 Structure of the thesis**

279 The thesis is segmented into seven chapters. Chapter one (Introduction) gives the background of
280 community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga Area of the
281 Okavango Delta, Botswana. The gap that the study intended to fill is highlighted in the introduction
282 chapter. The chapter also outlines the objectives and the significance of the study. Chapter two
283 (Literature Review) discusses literature relating to local community participation, the typology of
284 participation, natural resources conservation and means of community participation. It also
285 presents the conceptual framework which outlines relationships between factors influencing
286 community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives. Chapter three outlines the methods
287 used for data collection and analysis. It provides a description of the study area, research design,
288 sampling, data collection, data analysis and ethical considerations. The subsequent chapters
289 present the results as follows; Chapter four assesses socio-cultural factors influencing local
290 community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives, Chapter five analyses the influence
291 of management strategies on local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives,
292 while Chapter six assesses the influence of household economic trade-offs on local community
293 participation in wildlife conservation initiatives. The last Chapter (seven) provides a synthesis of
294 the results.

295 **CHAPTER 2**

296 **LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK**

297 **2.1 Literature review**

298 Since the 1990's, rural communities living inside and in fringes of wilderness areas have had their
299 livelihoods impacted by loss of access to resources and being forced to forgo their ancient
300 consumptive use of resources including hunting and gathering or clearing land for agricultural
301 purposes (Healy, 1994; Kelleher, Bleakley, & Wells, 1995; Moswete & Thapa, 2018), ideally for
302 conservation objectives (Mbaiwa, 2015; Wesche, 1996; Wood, 1998). The engagement of
303 community perspectives and perceptions in natural resource management has gained momentum
304 since then (Lynam, De Jong, Sheil, Kusumanto, & Evans, 2007). In spite of recent discussions and
305 incorporation of community participation in natural resources conservation, community
306 participation as a concept dates back to the mid-1950s (Kilewo & Frumence, 2015; Nelson &
307 Wright, 1995; Nour, 2011). To date, community participation is becoming more recognized as a
308 crucial component in decision making processes across all disciplines (Chan, 2016). This section
309 discusses the concept of community participation, factors influencing participation and how it has
310 been applied in natural resources conservation including conservation of wildlife.

311
312 **2.1.1 Local community participation**

313 The term “local communities” has diverse meanings, depending on the context and level of
314 communication. In Merriam-Webster dictionary, the word “community” is defined as “people with
315 common interests living in a particular area” or “a body of persons or nations having a common
316 history or common social, economic, and political interests” amongst others. The word itself is
317 very encircling that it may remain broad in definition. Chan (2016) maintained that a community
318 commonly constitutes people’s geographical proximity to an object of interest, either tangible or

319 intangible, and their shared commitment to a jointly defined goal or product. Wong, (2018) made
320 a reference to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)
321 Operational Guidelines of 1972, showing that the word community is interchangeable in use with
322 “local communities, non-governmental organizations and other interested parties and partners,
323 general public, civil society, local people”, “international community” and other associated words
324 of close meaning.

325
326 In this study local community refers to people with common interests and residing in a particular
327 area. Community participation as a form of public participation and refers to the engagement of
328 local communities in decision-making including the analysis of challenges and problems, setting
329 goals, creation of strategies and formulation of procedures in and for the management of natural
330 resources within the communities’ localities. According to the World Bank (1996: pp. xi) public
331 participation is defined as “a process through which stakeholders can influence and share control
332 over development initiatives and the decisions and resources that affect them” (Bishop & Davis,
333 2002: pp. 15; World Bank, 1996: pp. xi). This study adopt the World Bank definition of
334 participation which is a collaboration between authorities and the local communities to analyse a
335 problem, set objective, create a strategy and formulate procedures (Bishop & Davis, 2002).

336
337 Literature has argued that public participation is best understood as a discontinuous set of
338 techniques, chosen according to the issue in hand and the political imperative of the times
339 (Mutandwa & Gadzirayi, 2007; Pant, Dhakal, Pradhan, Leverington, & Hockings, 2016; Pettigrew
340 et al., 2012; Tosun, 1999; Zyambo, 2018). Participatory development is meant to empower socially
341 and economically marginalised people by increasing their involvement in decision-making
342 processes with the assumption of building their skills and confidence to analyse their situation,

343 reach consensus, make decisions and take action, so as to improve their circumstances (Guijt &
344 Shah, 1997). Participatory approaches also aims to achieve development trough sustainable use of
345 resources with by enforcing local community ownership and tenure right with strong institutional
346 structures (Murphree, 1996).

347 348 **2.1.2 Typology of participation**

349 Participation in modern society can be practiced in different forms. The participation type or level
350 describes the kind of opportunity given to the majority of the society or community in making key
351 decisions on issues that directly affect them (Carpentier, 2012; Quick & Bryson, 2016; Wong,
352 2018). The forms are usually executed through holding public meetings, conducting surveys, and
353 establishing citizen’s advisory committees (Chan, 2016). The end products of community
354 participation comes in different levels, forming a continuum (Hung et al., 2011). The different
355 levels are referred to, in literature, as “typology of participation” (Arnstein, 1969; Pretty, 1995;
356 Tosun, 1999). Community participation has been applied and used differently in various fields like
357 tourism development process (Tosun, 1999), participatory development approaches (Jones &
358 Kardan, 2013; López, Cajiao, Mejia, Durán, & Díaz, 2019; Pretty, 1995), and health (Kilewo &
359 Frumence, 2015; Marzuki, 2015).

360
361 Throughout decades there has been scholarly development of typologies of participation primarily
362 by Arnstein (1969), Pretty (1995), Tosun (1999) and others. The most cited typology of
363 participation to date is one developed by Arnstein (1969) though currently considered to be
364 outdated (Reed, 2008; Reed et al., 2018). More recent research supports and extends the concept
365 developed by Arnstein (1969), who is considered one of the pioneers of participation research.
366 Arnstein (1969), developed an eight rung ladder to represent the levels of participation being:

367 manipulation, therapy, informing, consultation, placation, partnership, delegated power, and
368 citizen control, named “Ladder of citizen participation” (Figure 1). Arnstein (1969) further
369 classified these rungs into three categories being non-participation, tokenism, and citizen power.
370

371

372 **Figure 1: Ladder of citizen participation**

373 Source: Arnstein (1969)

374

375 Moving up the ladder, community power, independence and control increases from manipulation
376 to citizen control (Arnstein, 1969). Manipulation and therapy fall under the classification of
377 nonparticipation where community members are educated or treated without their input.
378 Informing, consultation, and placation are considered to be tokenism, and, in this classification,
379 communities are merely advisers in the decision-making processes. Lastly, partnership, delegated
380 power and citizen control fall under citizen power , where communities have all the power and
381 independence in the decision-making processes. Hung et al. (2011) opined that typologies

382 organised by Arnstein (1969) have breadth of locus of control with higher degree of citizen control
383 at one end of the scale and non-participation at the other end.

384
385 Another typology of participation portrayed by Pretty (1995) had a wide range of levels being
386 manipulative participation, passive participation, participation by consultation, participation for
387 material incentives, functional participation, interactive participation, and self-mobilization.
388 Manipulative, passive, consultation and participation for material incentives were considered by
389 Hung et al. (2011) as all manipulation as the community members had no impact in making
390 decisions concerning their well-being. In functional participation, there is external pressure on
391 local communities to organise into groups for them to be involved in decision-making.
392 Unfortunately, external agencies might frame local communities in serving their interests under
393 functional participation (Pretty, 1995). Interactive participation on the other hand has local
394 communities and government jointly analysing, developing action plans, and forming community
395 organisations that have control over decision-making. In self-mobilisation, communities
396 independently organise and take control over decision-making on how resources are used (Pretty,
397 1995).

398
399 Tosun (1999) also developed a simplified typology of participation with three categories, being
400 spontaneous participation; induced participation; and coercive participation. Spontaneous
401 participation is at the high end of the continuum, in which participants are voluntarily and
402 independently active in solving their problems without external support. In this typology,
403 participants are highly motivated and are actively involved in the decision-making processes.
404 According to Tosun (1999), spontaneous participation can be termed as either direct, informal or
405 authentic participation depending on different instances though there are underlying

406 commonalities. In the middle of the continuum, there is induced participation which according to
407 Tosun (1999) is most common in developing countries where governments plays a central role in
408 management of common resources and initiating participatory action.

409
410 In induced participation, decision-making processes are formally mandated and endorsed by the
411 central government, by motivating and training locals to undertake leadership roles, building
412 community-based organisations, and supporting civic organisations. Terms like passive, indirect,
413 formal and pseudo participation are usually used in literature (Tosun, 1999). Lastly, there is
414 coercive participation which is at the lower end of the continuum in which participation is
415 compulsory and manipulative. In coercive participation, local communities do not have control
416 over and are not involved in decision-making and authorities independently implement policies. It
417 is also termed oppression, narrow participation, manipulative and therapy in literature (Arnstein,
418 1969; Jepson et al., 2013; Jones & Kardan, 2013; Tosun, 1999). Coercive participation, and to a
419 certain extent induced participation, may yield results immediately but in the long run are
420 counterproductive as they can erode community interests in development processes (Tosun, 1999).

421
422 Agarwal (2001) also developed another typology of participation though mostly drawn from
423 previous typologies by Pretty (1995) and White (1996). Contrary to earlier studies, Agarwal
424 (2001) assumed that the level of participation is defined by the extent of community's activeness,
425 not by how groups are initiated or formed. To achieve desired participation levels, the processes
426 will involve shifting from levels with low to high community activeness. The types of participation
427 as described by Agarwal (2001) are nominal, passive, consultative, activity-specific, active and
428 interactive participation (Table 1).

429

430 **Table 1: Typology of participation**

<i>Form/Level of participation</i>	<i>Characteristic features</i>
<i>Nominal participation</i>	Membership in the group
<i>Passive participation</i>	Being informed of decisions <i>ex post facto</i> ; or attending meetings and listening in/on decision-making, without speaking up
<i>Consultative participation</i>	Being asked an opinion in specific matters without guarantee of influencing decisions
<i>Activity-specific participation</i>	Being asked to (or volunteering to) undertake specific tasks
<i>Active participation</i>	Expressing opinions, whether or not solicited, or taking initiatives of other sorts
<i>Interactive (empowering) participation</i>	Having voice and influence in the group's decisions

431 Source: Agarwal (2001)

432

433 Typology by Agarwal (2001) seems to suit the definitions of participation adopted in this thesis
 434 as it discusses only scenarios where there is definable participation. Unlike other typologies, only
 435 forms where there is engagement of communities in a certain way are defined and categorised,
 436 ignoring instances where there is no visible form of participation like manipulation. Furthermore,
 437 Agarwal (2001) acknowledges that any desirable form of participation may have limitations on
 438 what it can achieve given imperative socio-economic and political dynamics of a community.
 439 Currently there is a clash on what different scholars opine to be actual participation. The dilemma
 440 is on whether the proposed participation types displace or extend already existing dialogue
 441 mechanisms across different community circumstances (Bishop & Davis, 2002).

442

443 It is suggested that a desired form of participation for a particular community may not necessarily
 444 work in another community. Therefore, the definition and application of any kind of participation

445 may vary due to the philosophical context in which it is applied. Participation is largely ideological
446 and dependent on the social and political connotations of a community (Tosun, 1999). According
447 to literature, for every form of participation that was implemented, producing good environmental
448 and social outcomes, there is an example of one that has gone wrong in another community (Reed,
449 2008; Reed et al., 2018). Therefore, Reed et al. (2018) suggested that there is need to analyse why
450 different forms of participation may work in a certain community and not work on the other.

451 452 **2.1.3 Natural resources conservation**

453 Conservation is defined as simply “prevention of wasteful use of a resource”, according to Oxford
454 dictionary. It is the “preservation, protection, or restoration of the natural environment and of
455 wildlife” and the word is commonly used in nature conservation, which is the preservation of
456 nature. According to Mascia et al., (2003, pp: 649), nature conservation or biodiversity
457 conservation is “about people as much as it is about species or ecosystems”. Studies also shows
458 that conservation is a human effort as it is “initiated by humans, designed by humans, and intended
459 to modify human behaviour”, it is primarily about people and their choices (Mascia et al., 2003 in
460 Schultz, 2011, pp: 1080). For example, out of self-realisation, communities at villages level in
461 India developed their local institutions that manages forest resources for sustainable use and
462 benefit (Nayak & Berkes, 2008; Sinha & Singh, 2011).

463
464 Conservation involves government of resources by people with rules and regulations through
465 institutions and organisations. Through engaging in conservation activities, people benefit from
466 sustainable use of available resources in their surrounding environment (Nkala, Mango, & Zikhali,
467 2011). Due to increasing human population and consequent intense competition for resources,
468 leading to threats of resources depletion and extinction of species it is important to prioritise

469 conservation (Chan, 2016). However, if conservation exclude use of resources by locals on their
470 livelihoods, then it is not good for them because they bear the costs of a process that benefits the
471 global commons (Berkes, 2006). This kind of conservation is common around the world whereby
472 the ownership of resources is on the state, and communities around have no access to use while
473 bearing the costs. For example, global high value species like lions and tigers pose threats and
474 costs to adjacent communities including loss of life, livestock depredation and associated
475 opportunity costs without or with minimal mitigation (Harihar, Veríssimo, & MacMillan, 2015;
476 McManus et al., 2015).

477

478 **2.1.4 Community participation and natural resources conservation**

479 Healy (1994) stressed that community participation is essential for successful management of
480 wildlife protected areas through involvement of indigenous people. Murphree (1996) also argued
481 that projects which seek to link conservation and development should shift towards development
482 by focusing on giving authority and responsibility over resources to local communities. On the
483 basis of these studies, scholars in the field concluded that success of conservation initiatives are
484 predicated by level of local community perception and support, which consequently reflects on
485 their level of participation (Lynam et al., 2007; Reed, 2008). As a direct result, Kilewo and
486 Frumence (2015) investigated some factors impeding community participation in developing and
487 implementing health programmes, which led to the additional conclusion that improved
488 involvement of communities is very essential for better outputs. Nonetheless, the broad literature
489 has made continuous efforts defining the concept of participation in general.

490

491 The findings by Healy (1994) and Murphree (1996) have led scholars to understand that engaging
492 and empowering local communities in management of their natural resources is essential for

493 successful conservation and development. More recent research supports and extends this concept
494 by emphasising the importance of exercising community participation as a process of fairly
495 evaluating social values, addressing needs and distribution of essential resources (Marzuki, 2015).
496 Marzuki (2015: pp. 26) further proved that on average, community engagement is “strongly and
497 significantly related to better performance” of community initiatives amid associated costs.
498 Likewise, Musavengane and Simatele (2016) concluded that the past and present exclusion of local
499 communities in natural resources conservation is unjust as the process directly affects their
500 livelihoods, henceforth advocating for promotion of strongly nurtured community participation.
501 Wondirad (2017) added that, in ecotourism development as an example, creating and ensuring a
502 clear platform for local communities to participate is both important to benefit locals and for
503 success of the initiative.

504
505 The comprehensive understandings of community participation depict it as a radical dynamic
506 process. Participation has been identified in different forms that vary in terms of level of
507 community enfranchisement enabled by appropriate policies and institutions (Kull, 2002). Lamsal,
508 Pant, Kumar and Atreya (2015) supported arguments by Pimbert and Pretty (1997) that legitimate
509 policies and institutions which democratically articulate the inclusion of local communities in
510 management and use of natural resources make conservation more socio-economically and
511 ecologically sustainable. The inclusiveness of administration of natural resources has been
512 reported to have influence in developing compliance of local communities and ensuring long term
513 benefits to both conservation and rural development (Andrade & Rhodes, 2012; Lamsal et al.,
514 2015; Pimbert & Pretty, 1997). Institutions and local organisations are crucial in facilitating
515 collective action and coordination including management of natural resources. Entities of
516 collectively organised locals, in the form of institutions are advanced and accepted as a platform

517 to fairly deliberate on “interests, problems, goals, and aspirations” for rural communities (Arntzen,
518 2005; Arntzen et al., 2003; Mbaiwa, 2013; Moswete & Thapa, 2018).

519
520 Overtime, the contextual connection between local communities and management of natural
521 resources has been regarded as crucial phenomenon though highly contested and complicated
522 (Rasoolimanesh, Jaafar, Ahmad, & Barghi, 2017; Su & Wall, 2014). Nonetheless, literature shows
523 that there has been growing interest in research and policy development focusing in natural
524 resource management and emergence of initiatives engaging communities (Katerere et al., 2001;
525 Mutandwa & Gadzirayi, 2007; Thakadu, 2005). Governments and institutions in some parts of the
526 world are moving towards empowering communities in achieving their conservation goals (Sinha
527 & Singh, 2011). Many governments are moving towards instilling the sense of resources
528 ownership and belonging in their communities by slowly moving from centralised management of
529 resources (Rahman, Hickey, & Sarker, 2012). For example, the government of India and similarly
530 of Tanzania, in recognizing the importance of community participation had introduced Joint Forest
531 Management (JFM) with the mandate of setting up working partnership between state and resource
532 users in rehabilitating degraded land through formation of village level committees (Kajembe,
533 Nduwamungu, & Luoga, 2004; Sinha & Singh, 2011).

534
535 On tourism, for example, literature shows that it adversely affects the social and cultural substance
536 of local communities (Brandon, 1996; Stem et al., 2010). Brandon (1996) stated that the most
537 potentially serious impact to local communities is due to “commodification” of culture, wherein
538 their cultures become marketable commodities in tourism. Some ecotourism operations are
539 considered to contribute minimally to local development, with little or no revenue reaching local
540 people, and those who benefit often rely upon an unstable source of income which is subject to

541 seasonal fluctuations, and also prone to economic and political risks (Bookbinder, Dinerstein,
542 Rijal, & Cauley, 1998; Healy, 1994; McLaren, 1998; Stem et al., 2010; Wood, 1998). Hemson,
543 MacLennan, Mills, Johnson, and Macdonald (2009) noted that even though revenue from tourism
544 in Botswana is divided among the operators, the government and the local communities, resource
545 lease arrangements with local communities are essentially voluntary agreements and the amounts
546 involved are not mandated by law.

547

548 **2.1.5 Means of community participation**

549 In the context of this study some definitions and typologies of community participation have been
550 discussed. Generally, participation has been defined as an action or practice of identifying and
551 incorporating stakeholders to take part in a particular development and influence the outcomes
552 (Bishop & Davis, 2002; Wong, 2018). Chan (2016) also described public participation as a
553 collaborative route in which the affected community is involved in the decision-making process
554 through public meetings, surveys, and open houses. Through these participation channels, people
555 have the opportunity to be involved in decision-making processes, especially in matters that may
556 affect their social well-being (Chan, 2016; Wong, 2018). Considering the ambiguity of nature of
557 community participation, Tosun (1999) denotes it as a complex issue involving different
558 philosophical and political opinions, institutional engagements and varying insights for
559 opportunities, and these are considered as “means of community participation” in this thesis.

560

561 Also, individuals personal characteristics, such as knowledge, awareness, resources and education
562 are considered factors influencing means of community participation as they influence
563 participation decisions, and collectively determines the direction and intensity of participation
564 behaviour (Cole, 2006). Hung et al. (2011) through the integrative motivation, opportunity, and

565 ability (MOA) model of community participation suggested that community members’
566 participation in tourism development and planning, for example, depends on both power
567 relationships and personal factors. The MOA model which Hung et al., (2011) tested its efficacy
568 outline the factors can be grouped to motivation, opportunity and ability as means of participation
569 and the resultant outcome being a certain participation level depending on intensity of the means.
570 Studies in the field can be either “means” or “ends” oriented depending on whether the study
571 analyses factors leading to participation or analyses the level of participation at a point in time.
572 This study focuses on analysing means of participation, and the kind of these studies offer
573 understanding over stakeholders’ characteristics on decision-making processes (Hung et al., 2011).

574
575 The recent work of Bango and Xelelo (2017) provide convincing evidence that lack of community
576 participation in the conservation activities can be a conflict and burden to both local population
577 development and conservationists, though the precise conditions under which this occurs remains
578 unknown. For example, the work of Bennett and Dearden (2014) showed very clearly that in
579 improving conservation and development outcomes, there is need to take into account root causes
580 of broad array of issues, but stopped short of identifying the causal factors and their relations to
581 the extent of the outcomes. Stone and Stone (2011) were similarly short on their attempts to explain
582 challenges and prospects of community participation in management of the Khama Rhino
583 Sanctuary Trust (KRST). They could not deliberate on community social, economic, cultural, and
584 administrative characteristics in relation to their impact and influence on evidently insignificant
585 level of participation yet admitting its usefulness.

586
587 Those social, economic, cultural, and administrative characteristics are the drivers or “means” of
588 community participation in natural resources management. The limited number of studies about

589 these drivers locally creates a gap in the understanding of dynamics leading to effective community
590 participation. Such lack of understanding has recently been highlighted as a problem by
591 Musavengane and Simatele (2016), as well as by Lamsal et al. (2015). Each of these researchers
592 underscored that progress in the field is highly unlikely until social networks and behaviors, and
593 economic perspectives that affect collective participation in conservation become known. There
594 are apparent challenges in generally applying the definition of factors without considering
595 divergent nature of socio-cultural, administrative, and economic conditions that can influence
596 different levels of participation and determine outcomes of initiatives (Tosun, 1999).

597
598 Identifying factors influencing community participation is very important for policy development
599 as socio-cultural, administrative and economic features vary per communities' spatial-temporal
600 conditions (Anderies, Janssen, & Ostrom, 2004; Martín-López et al., 2017). Policies and
601 programmes applied elsewhere cannot be borrowed and replicated in different places, but rather
602 be formulated considering conditions of local factors for adaptability (Martín-López et al., 2017).
603 In analysing community participation in world heritage sites (WHS) conservation initiatives,
604 Rasoolimanesh et al. (2017) acknowledged the importance of thoroughly understanding factors
605 that could influence communities to participate as those factors have significant impact in the
606 development and sustainability of conservation programs. It is also unfitting to therefore narrowly
607 identify and characterise those socio-cultural, administrative and economic features in separation
608 of ecological systems that link them to form a whole complex system (Ostrom, 2009).

609
610 In anticipation of this, Thakadu (2005) noted that it is necessary to appropriately recognise and
611 address these factors as they have an impact on the degree to which a community will contribute
612 to natural resource management or conservation strategies. To resolve this widely recognized

613 problem, this thesis analysed the magnitude, diversity, and impact of drivers of community
614 participation in conservation initiatives from both socio-economic and natural resource
615 management perspectives. That allowed greater understanding of level and role of community
616 participation in influencing livelihoods outcomes and community development through
617 conservation. This required conceptualisation of community social bargaining for understanding
618 of social structure and the application of the MOA model to capture drivers of community
619 participation in alignment with the means (motivation, opportunity, and ability) of participation
620 for analysis purposes.

621
622 In summary, considerable support for concepts reviewed in this section derives from: 1) social
623 capital studies (Musavengane & Simatele, 2016; Perkins, Hughey, & Speer, 2002); 2) participation
624 studies (Noe & Kangalawe, 2015; Reed et al., 2018); and, 3) research on efficacy of MOA model
625 (Hung, Sirakaya-Turk, & Ingram, 2011; Jepson, Clarke, & Ragsdell, 2013; Rasoolimanesh et al.,
626 2017). The body of work reviewed indicated a need to identify the social, economic, cultural, and
627 institutional characteristics of communities and how they influence the level of participation in
628 natural resource management. Community participation has a significant impact in legitimising
629 processes of policy formulation and review, capacity building strategies and mobilization
630 approaches for conservation initiatives and the support and success of conservation initiatives and
631 rural development. Earlier studies supported the need for such research and provided strong
632 support for the importance of accruing knowledge about the subject. Recent findings by Jepson et
633 al. (2013) also supported the need for such research.

634

635 **2.2 Conceptual framework**

636 The conceptualisation of factors in this thesis was informed mainly by the motivation-opportunity-
637 ability (MOA) model of community participation in analysing factors influencing community
638 participation. To concurrently integrate the ecological factors when analysing socio-cultural,
639 administrative, and economic factors underlying communities' decision making to partake in
640 conservation initiatives, social-ecological systems (SES) framework was used explicitly in
641 conceptualisation of factors. Both concepts guided the study in assessment of local communities'
642 reactive factors and characteristics towards support and participation in conservation initiatives in
643 relation to outcomes of conservation and subsequent livelihoods. The concepts guided the analysis
644 of drivers of communities as actors to take the initiative to participate in conservation from an
645 individual's behavioural perspective and resource management perspective. Separately MOA
646 model and the SES framework are discussed in the following sub-sections with their constructual
647 linkages within and between them.

648

649 ***2.2.1 Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) framework***

650 The motivation-opportunity-ability (MOA) model of community participation was first raised in
651 the late 1980's to model the behaviour of consumers in decision-making (MacInnis & Jaworski,
652 1989). The model has been evolving over time being used from different fields. From a theoretical
653 perspective, the MOA model synthesizes participation research by emphasizing commonalities
654 found in studies from several fields, including advertising, consumer behavior, tourism, and public
655 participation (Hung et al., 2011; Jepson et al., 2013). Participants in all applications of the model
656 are engaged in a decision-making process. In this study, the MOA model was used to inform
657 conceptualisation of drivers of communities in decision-making process to participate in
658 conservation and their level of influence leading to different conservation and livelihood outcomes.

Figure 2: An integrative model for community participation

Source: Hung et al. (2011).

659

660

661

662

663 The features of motivation, opportunity, and ability, as shown up in Figure 2 above, builds up the

664 MOA model as means of participation and have been highlighted to be critical in influencing

665 decision-making in participation (Hung et al., 2011). Individuals' choice of whether to participate

666 or not depends on both availability of benefits, communication and interpretation of information,

667 and perceived opportunity (Foley, 2008). According to the integrative MOA model, the variability

668 of community participation levels, referred to as ends of participation, are dependent on change

669 and situation on the means therein referred to as features or antecedents (Hung et al., 2011). The

670 prediction, analysis and characterisation of incidences of levels and intensities of motivation,

671 ability and opportunity can be used to illustrate various influences and outcomes of participation

672 (Hung et al., 2011).

673

674 The factors of motivation, opportunity and ability influence participation differently depending on

675 community socio-economic, cultural and political and individuals personal conditions (Hung et

676 al., 2011; Tosun, 1999). Also the influence depend on the level of intensities of those factors. The

677 success or failure of societies in issues of common ground depends on their ability in solving
678 mutual problems of collective action (National Research Council, 2002; Ostrom & Ahn, 2003).
679 Studies have previously highlighted the importance of motivation in driving individuals decision
680 to participate (Jepson et al., 2013). It can affect the intensity and direction of the behaviour of
681 decision making. Opportunity on the other hand is defined as circumstances that facilitates
682 community involvement in participation process. It provides platform in form of channel of
683 communication between community and government (Jepson et al., 2013).

684
685 Lastly, the other aspect of the MOA model is ability which Jepson et al. (2013) regarded as the
686 most complex entity comprising combination of factors such as “awareness, experience,
687 knowledge, skills, accessibility to information and financial resources” (Jepson et al., 2013: pp.
688 191). Though scholars such as Cole (2006) advocate for high community participation in decision-
689 making processes, that might not be desirable and applicable as communities might lack the
690 necessary skills and knowledge to participate in such informed exercise (Jepson et al., 2013;
691 Tosun, 1999). That simply illustrates the importance of ability as a fundamental factor in
692 community participation levels. It is highlighted that even though members of communities might
693 have both the motivation and opportunity to participate, they might be hindered by lack of ability
694 to do so (Jepson et al., 2013).

695
696 Hung et al., (2011) concluded that, factors of motivation, opportunity, and ability proposed in the
697 MOA framework are critical determinants of participation decisions within a community. The
698 MOA framework just like other behavioural and decision making theories focuses on socio-
699 economic characteristics of communities towards decision making. The skeleton of the
700 frameworks does not clearly lay out the ecological factors that might affect the premises on which

701 decisions and choices are based. That reason might render the framework insufficient in these study,
702 but it was used to form a foundation for making analysis of individuals and community internal
703 characteristics towards decision making. To compliment this shortcoming the framework was used
704 concurrently with the Social-Ecological systems (SES) framework in conceptualising the factors.

705

706 **2.2.2 Social-Ecological systems (SES) framework**

707 The SES framework is formed by interconnected human systems and ecosystems (Dressel,
708 Ericsson, & Sandström, 2018; Martín-López et al., 2017). SES framework is one of the
709 frameworks brought by research scientists together with frameworks like Human-Environment
710 systems (HES), to bridge the gap in fostering understanding between social and ecological
711 problems and their surrounding interactions (Binder, Hinkel, Bots, & Pahl-Wostl, 2013; Zhao &
712 Wen, 2012). Initially the understanding of complex social and ecological interactive functions
713 were limited due to narrow disciplinary boundaries and SES came as an answer (Zhao & Wen,
714 2012). Previously in literature, SES has been since defined as linked systems of human and nature,
715 underscoring that humans are considered to be part of the ecosystem, not apart from it or related
716 somehow (Berkes, Folke, & Colding, 1998; Ostrom, 2009).

717

718 The SES framework was initially proposed by Ostrom (2007) adapting and evolving it from the
719 institutional analysis and development (IAD) framework (Ostrom, 2011). The SES relies on the
720 foundation of IAD framework and the two are closely associated and related (McGinnis & Ostrom,
721 2014). IAD framework has been used in the past few decades to address difficulties found in policy
722 analysis. The framework provide guidance for identifying problems and challenges in management
723 of shared resources in institutional and collective action arenas and their resulting effects (Nigussie
724 et al., 2018; Ostrom, 2007). The IAD framework has been extensively used in research and

725 development planning to analyse and study management of common resources at local level
726 (Benson, Jordan, Cook, & Smith, 2013; Nigussie et al., 2018). It is agreed that in tourism industry
727 for example, the management of the system need to creates value for it by accommodating all
728 actors being tourists, private operators, public institutions and organisations, and local
729 communities (Martini, Buffa, & Notaro, 2017).

730
731 Though it remains a work in progress for now, McGinnis and Ostrom (2014) demonstrates that
732 SES framework is at advanced stages and can be used by scholars to analyse a variety of resources
733 dynamics across different settings. according to McGinnis and Ostrom (2014), the supposition of
734 the SES framework is that “humans can make conscious choices as individuals or as members of
735 collaborative groups, and that these individual and collective choices can, at least potentially, make
736 a significant difference in outcomes”. For the purposes of this study, social systems on the SESs
737 framework are considered to include governance of resources through institutions, policies,
738 governmental and non-governmental organisations by the concerned actors. The natural or
739 ecological system mainly comprises natural resources in terms of wildlife and their land habitat,
740 and both systems characteristics are linked and interrelated in influence and functioning (Carter et
741 al., 2014). Lack of reliable information about interactions of human and nature in context of social
742 characteristics can be associated with illegitimate and worthless conservation actions (Leenhardt
743 et al., 2015).

744

745

746 **Figure 3: Social-Ecological Systems (SES) framework by Ostrom (2009)**

747 Sources: Johnson et al. (2019); McGinnis and Ostrom (2014).

748

749 The linkages and processes of the complex system occurs over and across different scales with
 750 unique up-and-coming properties (Leenhardt et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2007). And that is what the
 751 SES framework is built up of. The linkages include the services provided by nature to human
 752 activities and actions, and the effect of governance influences on both the social and ecological
 753 sub-systems and units (Figure 3). Components in the SES framework provide feedback to each
 754 other as interactions (I), the first tier variables, and system performance outcomes (O) are
 755 consequently influenced by actors (A) in the system, the system governance (GS) approaches, and
 756 both ecological resource system (RS) and units (RU) (Dressel et al., 2018; McGinnis & Ostrom,
 757 2014). Beyond that, there are second tier variables contained under each first-tier variable, not
 758 depicted on the SES framework figure, including economic developments, technology, location,
 759 government and non-government organisations, collective choice rules, socioeconomic attributes,
 760 and others. The human and nature systems are interdependent, nested within these many secondary

761 tier predictive factors that can influence participation. The ecosystem provides all human needs in
 762 form of “material products, environment regulation, culture functions” thus implying the effects
 763 human activities can have in the ecosystem (Zhao & Wen, 2012: pp. 1384).

764
 765 **2.2.3 Factors influencing community participation**

766 The factors in the conceptual framework below (Figure 4) include Governance systems (GS),
 767 Actors (A), and Social, Economic, and Political settings (S) which form the social systems part of
 768 the SES framework. The factors are linked to means of participation from the integrative
 769 motivation-opportunity-ability (MOA) model of community participation.

770

771

772 **Figure 4: Conceptual framework on drivers of participation in conservation**

773 Sources: Developed with insights from Hung et al. (2011), Johnson et al. (2019), McGinnis &
 774 Ostrom (2014), and Ostrom (2009)

775

776 Actors in the framework include organised and distinct local communities, and organisations with
 777 their socio-economic attributes, location in relation to resources, leadership and characteristics of
 778 the technology used. The actors, who are stakeholders in the interaction (I) process of participation
 779 base their social bargaining on available platform, which is the governance system. The

780 governance system as a platform provides the actors (community) with the necessary opportunity
781 to take part in conservation. Both actors and governance systems are directly interlinked with the
782 social, economic, and political systems, which forms the whole social systems part of the SESs
783 framework. The governance systems are directly linked to actors as much as they affect their
784 bargaining in decision making. Carter et al., (2014: pp 2) maintained that collectively well
785 organised communities “can shape and be shaped by policies and norms” that guides or impact
786 processes or operations of their common interest. Thus, justifying the direct link from governance
787 systems to both actors and their social bargaining and the feedback from social bargaining to both
788 actors and the governance system. Actors independently do not influence the governing system
789 but rather as a collective or organised, thus no feedback from actors to governance system but
790 rather from social bargaining.

791
792 The social capital have a direct influence on the means of participation being motivation to
793 participate, opportunities available in participating and the collective ability to participate within
794 the social bargaining arena. For a more comprehensive understanding of the ecological influences
795 of communities to participate in collective action, the aspect of social capital is considered in
796 analysing the linkages between individuals and group behaviour variations towards collective
797 action within the social bargaining. It is specified that, for communities to engage in participation,
798 they need to be collectively well organised and connected to commonly make a decision (Parrott,
799 2011). Social capital has been referred to as a resource base individuals have access to through
800 their connection with others (van Beuningen & Schmeets, 2013). Societies have the confidence to
801 invest in collective activities, trusting to gain support from others and avoid engaging in boundless
802 actions with undesirable outcomes (National Research Council, 2002; Pretty, 2003).

803

804 Figure four above illustrate that there is interactive linkage between the concept of social capital
805 and means of participation. This illustrates that all components have influence on each other and
806 the intensity of the other will affect the level and outcome of others. Motivation for example, brings
807 people together, that being social capital, towards achieving certain goals and desires, therefore
808 collectively engage with others, and that also creating a certain participation level in that course
809 (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017). Also in the framework above (Figure 4), motivation, opportunity
810 and ability as means of participation are influenced by the kind of actors or communities involved,
811 as much as they influence those actors to take participation decisions.

812
813 Participation and conservation forms the focal action situation of the conceptual framework above
814 (Figure 4). Within the SES framework, the focal action situation includes the interactions (I) which
815 directly leads to outcomes (O), conceptualised in the model as participation in conservation. The
816 interaction in participation includes the deliberative processes, information sharing, lobbying and
817 investment activities, and also monitoring and sanctioning activities (Johnson et al., 2019).
818 Conflict between and within the actors can also happen in the confines of the interaction process.
819 All that takes place in the interaction phase directly lead to outcomes. The outcomes includes both
820 social and ecological measures. In the conservation arena this will lead to activities and outcomes.
821 The outcomes have a feedback to the interaction process as they provide a measure which can
822 determine the sustainable or most productive kind of interaction.

823
824 This study analysed factors under social bargaining being motivation, opportunity and ability as
825 drivers of community participation in wildlife conservation. Social capital was considered to be
826 imbedded under each of the factors. Motivation was analysed through an objective which explored
827 household economic trade-offs as factors influencing local community participation in wildlife

828 conservation initiatives. It was assumed that communities were likely to participate when wildlife
829 conservation initiatives are relevant to upliftment of their household livelihoods through reducing
830 costs and promoting benefits of living alongside wildlife. A combination of factors including
831 awareness, experience, knowledge, skills, accessibility to information , and cultural norms and
832 values were considered to be influencing the ability of local communities to participate in wildlife
833 conservation initiatives. These factors were analysed under chapter four of the thesis. Lastly,
834 opportunity was analysed through the study of how formal management strategies influence local
835 community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives.

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CHAPTER 3
METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study area

The study was done in the Greater Seronga Area, which is in the eastern panhandle of the Okavango Delta, situated in Ngamiland District in north-western Botswana. The eastern Okavango Panhandle includes the main settlements of Seronga, Gunotsoga, Eretsha, Beetsha and Gudigwa which are chosen for the purposes of the study (Figure 5). The total population of the area is around 7,891 including associated localities (Central Statistics Office, 2012). These settlements have important areas of wetlands in flood plains and main river channels, commonly on the southwestern fringes and all are the only members of the Okavango Community Trust (OCT), a CBNRM organisation. Community-based conservation organisations and NGOs such as Eco-exist and CLAWS Conservancy focused on mitigating human-wildlife conflicts for the benefit of both local communities and wildlife conservation are running in the area. The Okavango Delta as a whole have diverse group of people in ethnicity and culture. The area consist of mainly about five ethnic groups including Dxeriku, Hambukushu, Wayei, Xanakwe (River bushmen) and Bugakwe (Khoe) each with their own language and identity (Bock & Johnson, 1993).

There is evidence of historical migration patterns of this ethnic groups as members of all the ethnic groups are present in neighbouring countries of Namibia, Angola, and Zambia. People from all the ethnic groups are spread throughout the Okavango Delta today, contrary to their historical patterns where the Bugakwe, Dxeriku, and Hambukushu occupied the Panhandle throughout to the north-eastern edge of the Delta (Bock & Johnson, 1993). The Xanekwe occupying the Panhandle, central and western Delta, and the Wayeyi occupying the northern, north-western, and the southern parts of the Delta. Since Botswana independence in 1966, people in the Okavango Delta just like others

860 around the country experienced cultural, political, social, and economic shift due to democratic
861 integration and developments.

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863

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Figure 5: Map showing five study site villages

865

866 The lush Okavango Delta was recently listed as the 1,000th UNESCO world heritage site as a
867 natural resource in 2014 (Keitumetse & Pampiri, 2016). The area is also part of the Kavango-
868 Zambezi (KAZA) Trans-frontier Conservation Area, which is a network of regional protected
869 areas that aims to increase community development, biodiversity conservation and expansion of
870 historical game migration routes that involves countries of Namibia, Botswana, Zambia,

871 Zimbabwe, and Angola. The Okavango Delta is rich in natural resources and is a habitat to wild
872 species of more than 1000 plants, 86 fish, 64 reptiles, 482 species of birds and 130 species of
873 mammals (Ramberg et al., 2006). The habitat is diverse and include: permanent and seasonal rivers
874 and lagoons; permanent swamps; seasonal and occasionally flooded grasslands; riparian forest;
875 dry woodlands and island communities surrounded by Kalahari savanna extending hundreds of
876 kilometres (Bock & Johnson, 1993). The region has semi-arid climate with three distinct seasons:
877 hot-dry (September–November), hot-wet (December–April), and cool-dry (May–August).
878 Temperatures ranges from 5⁰C in winter to summer heights of around 40⁰C, averaging annual 14⁰C
879 (min), 32⁰C (max) and, average annual precipitation of 450mm (Wolski, Todd, Murray-Hudson,
880 & Tadross, 2012).

881
882 The communities were selected for their geography, and natural resources dependencies and for
883 feasibility. The population is predominantly rural and remote with diverse livelihoods and high
884 intensity human-wildlife conflict (Kolawole et al., 2016). The landscape is concentrated with
885 wildlife and livestock, tourism, pastoral, arable farming (including flood recession cultivation-
886 *molapo* farming) activities and migration for wage labour providing the main economic activities.
887 An average of 45.9% of households are classified as poor in the greater Seronga area (Statistics
888 Botswana, 2015a) with an increasing unemployed adult population of 27% against a national
889 average of 17.63% (Statistics Botswana, 2015b). Prominent challenges in the district, including
890 animal diseases and human-wildlife conflict have since 1980s led to significant changes in land
891 use and policy related to the control of animals, wildlife management and tourism (Motsholapheko,
892 Kgathi, & Vanderpost, 2011). Evaluation and assessment of community organisations need to be
893 treated case-by-case to avoid missing key aspects of management and achievements (Mbaiwa &
894 Stronza, 2010; Stone & Stone, 2011), this support the selection of the study area.

895 **3.2 Research design**

896 This was an analytical, cross-sectional study focused on community participation in conservation
897 initiatives. Cross-sectional research design was employed because, unlike other designs like the
898 longitudinal design, it does not have time dimension and only rely on existing differences rather
899 than variations resulting from intervention or treatment (Labaree, 2021). The participants in this
900 design were not randomly selected, but rather picked based on existing differences being either at
901 village level or affiliation to an organisation of interest or particular grouping. The cross-sectional
902 design only measure differences between a variety of people, or phenomena rather than a process
903 of change. Therefore, the study employed a passive approach and made causal inferences and drew
904 conclusions from existing differences and relationships. The existence of community-based
905 organisations (CBOs), such as the Okavango Community Trust, in natural resource management
906 were of vital importance as views and opinions building up the data had a common ground and
907 point of reference, being these CBOs.

908
909 A mixed-methods approach, concurrent triangulation research design was employed in data
910 collection and analysis. Quantitative and qualitative data was collected and analysed differently
911 but complemented each other. The basis for this method was that both qualitative and quantitative
912 data collection and analysis methods were equally important. Therefore, this study employed
913 household survey (close-ended and open-ended questions) for both quantitative and qualitative
914 data collection, and interviews for qualitative data collection. The results were integrated on the
915 interpretation process to enable a more in-depth and rigorous visualisation and understanding of
916 the phenomena under investigation. This helped in validation of findings and creating a solid
917 foundation for drawing conclusions. Quantitative data was analysed through both descriptive and
918 inferential statistics, and qualitative through Keyword-In-Context (KWIC) analysis and thematic

919 analysis. Quantitative data analysis helped visualisation of changes and relationships in variables
920 while qualitative data analysis helped in gaining insightful patterns on factors influencing local
921 communities' decision-making experiences towards conservation initiatives.

922

923 **3.3 Sampling**

924 *Households survey sample*

925 Simple random sampling was used to select the households to be interviewed. A list of residential
926 plots (plot numbers) for all households in each village and village maps were obtained from the
927 Land Board offices in Seronga. Using residential plot numbers, undeveloped plots were eliminated
928 from the list using picture overlay on online Google Earth Maps and then removing plots without
929 visible structures from the plots list. Household listing was carried out through household
930 occupancy verification. All remaining households were numbered and the ones to be interviewed
931 were selected through a statistical randomiser. This ensured that each household had an equal
932 chance of being selected and reduced bias. The sample size was generated through a formula from
933 the total number of households in the study area. Factors used in the calculation included the
934 population size (total number of households) of 1651, confidence level of 0.05 (95%), and margin
935 of error of 0.06 ($\pm 6\%$) which gave a sample size of 248 households (Table 2). The Taro Yamane
936 sample size equation ($n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$) was used. With n for sample size, N for total population and e
937 for margin of error.

938

939

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941

942 **Table 2: Village population, total number of households and sample size per study site**

<i>Village</i>	<i>Village population*</i>	<i>Number of households*</i>	<i>Sample size</i>	<i>Sample percentage</i>
<i>Seronga</i>	2879	731	103	41.5
<i>Gunotsoga</i>	908	196	30	12.1
<i>Eretsha</i>	909	245	36	14.5
<i>Beetsha</i>	1530	343	48	19.4
<i>Gudigwa</i>	710	136	31	12.5
<i>Total</i>	<i>6936</i>	<i>1651</i>	<i>248</i>	<i>100</i>

943 Source: *Statistics Botswana (2015a)

944

945 *Key informants*

946 To select key informants, critical case purposive sampling method was used to select individuals
 947 from across the study site each being representatives of their villages or organisation (Robinson,
 948 2014). The informants were identified and selected by the researcher on the basis that they have
 949 influence and interest on participation in management of natural resources. The managers, village
 950 headmen and chairpersons were targeted for the purposes of the study. A list of all institutions and
 951 organisations in the study area was obtained or created (stakeholder mapping) and the stakeholders
 952 were contacted and visited to identify and nominate a representative to take part in the survey. In
 953 addition, a representative from every selected government institution or department was
 954 interviewed and the assumption was that the population was very small and did not need sampling.
 955 Total of fifteen key informants interviews were conducted and they included Ecoexist site
 956 manager, dikgosi for all the five villages, VDC chairperson's for all the five villages, OCT
 957 Manager, Problem-Animal-Control officer at the Department of Wildlife & National Parks based
 958 in Seronga, deputy chairperson for BoKhakhwee Trust (Gudigwa) - and board chairperson for
 959 OCT.

960

961 *Focus group discussants*

962 To get in-depth information about what influences communities to participate in wildlife
963 conservation related activities, focus group discussions were conducted. Household heads were
964 recruited during the survey and invited for a focus group discussion as a follow up relying on their
965 ability and capacity to provide the needed information. The ideal number of participants in the
966 focus group discussions was between six and eight (Nyumba, Wilson, Derrick, & Mukherjee,
967 2018), and that was the target on this study. Though there was no guarantee that all those invited
968 will attend, it was recommended to over-recruit by about 10 to 25%, therefore over recruitment of
969 ten to eleven participants was ideal.

970

971 The focus group discussions were done once in all the five villages of Seronga, Gunotsoga,
972 Eretsha, Beetsha and Gudigwa. This complemented the shortcoming that one focus group
973 discussion could not thoroughly explore the components of a topic of discussion, and exhaustively
974 discuss a topic, and a minimum of three to four group meetings were recommended. Focus group
975 discussions were used for data collection, mainly to understand people's perceptions as this is very
976 important in establishing why people responded to wildlife conservation issues in a certain way
977 and how that is related to their socio-economic status as a community. This also helped explore
978 the way people understood conservation initiatives, how they interpreted the information and
979 awareness materials from conservation management and finally how they accepted the
980 management initiatives as proper and suitable. In overall the focus group discussions were used to
981 assess the efficiency of conservation strategies currently in place in the greater Seronga area and
982 what drives communities to participate in such initiatives.

983

984 **3.4 Instrumentation**

985 *Household survey schedule*

986 The household survey used an interview schedule with close and open-ended questions, and five-
987 point Likert scale statements. The variables were measured through the use of continuous integers,
988 ordinal and nominal categories, Likert-scaled statements, and open-ended responses per
989 observation. Data was captured on respondents demographics and household characteristics
990 including gender of the respondent (nominal), age (continuous), occupation of respondent
991 (nominal), education level (nominal), gender, marital status of the respondent (nominal), age group
992 of respondents (nominal) ethnicity of household head (nominal), type of household (nominal),
993 occupation of respondent (nominal). Other variables captured were on household economic
994 activities including nature of alternative sources of income (nominal), number of household
995 members engaged in sources of livelihood activities (continuous), and annual cash income
996 (continuous). Data on agriculture and animal husbandry practices including type (nominal) and
997 number of livestock, types of agricultural holdings (nominal), possible threats to your farming
998 activities (nominal), compensation for any form of farm damages by wildlife(nominal),
999 satisfaction of compensation (nominal), household possess skills other than farming skills (open-
1000 ended). These variables were used commonly in meeting all the research objectives.

1001

1002 The household survey schedule also captured data on aspect of ability to fulfil the objective on the
1003 influence of socio-cultural factors on local community participation in wildlife conservation
1004 including whether the household own or have access to listed communication assets (nominal),
1005 wildlife conservation initiatives of their knowledge operating in the community (open-ended),
1006 whether wildlife conservation initiatives listed serve according to expectations (open-ended), 18

1007 Likert scaled statements on knowledge, awareness, cultural norms and values related to wildlife
1008 conservation. To explore the aspect of opportunities available for local communities to participate
1009 in wildlife conservation initiatives, data was captured specifically for the analysis of the influence
1010 of formal management strategies on local community participation in wildlife conservation
1011 including whether household members registered in any community organisation in the
1012 village(nominal), Is organisation concerned with wildlife conservation(nominal), organisation
1013 consider opinions during decision-making (nominal), satisfied with opinion uptake in organisation
1014 decision-making processes (nominal), name of platforms for engaging on dialog (open-ended),
1015 platforms to voluntarily channel opinions (open-ended), organisation registered on (open-ended),
1016 platforms to air views and opinions about wildlife conservation issues in your community (open-
1017 ended), aware of the existence of any community-based organisation (open-ended) and 14 Likert
1018 scaled statements on formal management processes on wildlife conservation initiatives.

1019
1020 Motivation as an important concept was analysed identifying benefits and participation through
1021 the assessment of the influence of household economic trade-offs on local community participation
1022 in wildlife conservation initiatives and the data collected included variables on household
1023 economic benefit from wildlife conservation initiatives (nominal), how the household benefit in
1024 participation (open-ended), satisfaction with level of benefits (nominal), issues considered before
1025 participating (nominal), whether take part in the management of wildlife resources (nominal), age
1026 group actively participating in wildlife conservation issues (nominal), how community in general
1027 participate in decision making processes on wildlife conservation (nominal), any factors limiting
1028 or impending access to use of natural resources (nominal, open-ended), how limitations affect
1029 household livelihood activities (open-ended) and 15 Likert scaled statements on household
1030 economic trade-offs and participation.

1031

1032 *Key informants interview guide*

1033 The purpose of conducting interviews was to reach out to key informants who gave more in-depth
1034 information on issues including. The interviews were guided by a list of open questions in
1035 sequentially logical form to cover all aspects of the subject. The questions were followed by probes
1036 where necessary to enable the respondent to elaborate on key issues. The questions captured data
1037 on the mandate of your organisation/institution represented by respondent, whether the
1038 organisation/institution is concerned with issues of wildlife conservation, and whether the
1039 organisation/institution concerned with issues of community welfare development. More in-depth
1040 information captured on whether organisations somehow help in group formations within
1041 communities to engage in wildlife conservation, if organisations are part of networks on wildlife
1042 conservation, and whether communities are engaged in the networks. The interview further
1043 gathered data on how key informants perceived the level of tolerance towards wildlife conservation
1044 initiatives in their community, and the attitudes of communities towards organisations and
1045 institutions that brings collective action towards wildlife conservation.

1046

1047 The interviews also captured data on available policies or processes that creates opportunities for
1048 communities to participate in wildlife conservation, whether local communities regard existing
1049 initiatives as legitimate in addressing conservation issues in their area and if they participate.
1050 Opinions were gathered on whether organisations ever host general meetings concerning wildlife
1051 conservation issues, and if they do how many meetings are hosted annually, whether individuals
1052 have the opportunity to say something during the meetings, how many meetings were about
1053 wildlife conservation issues whether the organisation takes opinions from local communities and
1054 if opinions from local communities help in improving wildlife conservation initiatives.

1055
1056 *Focus group discussions guide*

1057 The focus group discussions captured data on the current and desired level of participation from
1058 participants perspective through the voting game process. Steps for the voting game using the
1059 Spidergram tool (PARTICIPATION IN DISPLACEMENT WORKING GROUP, 2021) were as
1060 follows; introduce the exercise to the participants, and highlight that there are no wrong
1061 impressions, views and ideas and everything they have to say is important. Further on the steps the
1062 researcher showed the participants a diagram (Figure 6) on levels of participation, asked them what
1063 they see, make sure that everyone understood the same. Proceeded to ask where they currently see
1064 their level of participation at, and more detailed questions on this, to allow the participants to share
1065 freely, what is good and what is bad about that.

1066

1067
1068 **Figure 6: Levels of community engagement**

1069 Source: International Association for Public Participation (2015)

1070
1071 The researcher then explained that there will be a small voting exercise to understand better
1072 whether there is a need to change the manner in which they are engaged in wildlife conservation
1073 initiatives in the future. On the diagram, explained that one end represents a very low level of
1074 community engagement, and the other end represents a very high level of community engagement

1075 and explain that there are some levels in between. The researcher then gave the participants 3 green
1076 stickers and 3 yellow stickers each and explained what the different sticker colours stand for and
1077 mean to them. Proceeded to allow each person to place the stickers on the diagram and explain
1078 that each one will place the stickers according to their perceived level or levels of “participation”
1079 as discussed. Invited the first person to vote and asked why they chose to vote that to make sure
1080 that the vote is representing the reality – recorded the explanations given. Then counted all the
1081 stickers per level in front of the participants. Marked and noted the result, concluded on the results
1082 and feedback, discussed more on it. This activity was done over the five groups to properly
1083 evaluate their perceptions. And that was the end of the voting process. Further, points of
1084 discussions ignited by researcher were on participants perspective towards wildlife conservation
1085 initiatives (normal discussions) including a) conservation management initiatives of their
1086 knowledge, b) the appropriateness of such initiatives, c) the inclusiveness of the management
1087 initiatives and policies and d) desirability and attractiveness to participate in the initiatives.

1088

1089 **3.5 Data collection**

1090 *Household survey*

1091 Structured interview schedules were conducted by the researcher on face-to-face basis with
1092 household heads in the study area according to the sampling structure discussed above. Household
1093 heads were interviewed at their residence; in their absence, any adult member (≥ 21 years old)
1094 willing to participate were interviewed. The assumption was that the household head, or any adult
1095 taking the responsibilities of household head, were likely to be knowledgeable about the state of
1096 resources use and conservation in their area. The participants understood their household social

1097 and economic factors and also be able to give their opinion about the subject. The schedules were
1098 conducted in simple Setswana or English language according to the respondent's preference and
1099 the technical jargon was avoided.

1100
1101 The data collection process took around four weeks (three on household survey, one on key
1102 informants and focus group discussions) to complete. The household survey was conducted
1103 between August and September 2020. Each interview was timed, and none took more than 45
1104 minutes to complete. Prior to conducting the interview schedules, they were pre-tested for validity
1105 on a pilot sample at Sexaxa village which was considered to have similar characteristics to the
1106 study site. The pre-test involved briefing respondents on the purpose of the study and their rights
1107 along and after the interview. After completion of the pre-test, final adjustments were made.

1108
1109 *Key informant interviews*

1110 Key informant interviews were conducted, and an expert purposive sampling applied on selection,
1111 targeting chairpersons of Community based organisations (CBO), Village development
1112 committees (VDC), and farmers committees, the villages headmen, government employees and
1113 representatives of NGO's. Exploratory and in-depth interviews were conducted, directed by use of
1114 an interview schedule and the responses were captured through notes and voice recording (upon
1115 consent). The purpose being to get more in-depth information to supplement data from household
1116 survey and give a different perspective on mainly administrative issues in relation to the subject.

1117
1118 *Focus group discussions*

1119 The focus group discussions were conducted at once from each village after the completion of
1120 household surveys. A more convenient and neutral venue was used, such as a classroom or kgotla
1121 shelter. The venues identified provided the participants with comfort, were easily accessible and

1122 had assurance of minimal distraction to the discussions. The researcher facilitated the discussions
1123 together with an assistant who in the process observed the interactions. The researcher as the
1124 facilitator managed relationships and interactions within the group and also created a relaxed and
1125 conducive environment. The assistant's role was to observe and document the general content of
1126 the discussions through audio recording and notetaking. The duration of the discussions ranged
1127 between one hour and, one hour thirty minutes to cater for concentration lapse and fatigue.

1128 1129 **3.6 Data analysis**

1130 Data collected from the survey and key informant interviews were cleaned by checking for
1131 accuracy and errors. The data were entered into the computer through a developed documenting
1132 database that integrates the various measures. Quantitative data obtained from household survey
1133 through interview schedules was summarised using descriptive statistics. The Statistical Package
1134 for Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used to capture and analyse both quantitative and
1135 qualitative data from household surveys. The data including demographics and five-point Likert
1136 scale data were analysed using the software. The data was organised for visualisation using
1137 summary tables and graphs (histograms). Statistical tools used for descriptive analysis included
1138 the Univariate analysis to describe the distribution through measures of central tendencies
1139 (standard deviation) and dispersion (frequency distribution) of variables.

1140
1141 To make generalisations and make conclusions from the data on how and to what extent the factors
1142 measured influence communities to participate in conservation initiatives, inferential statistics
1143 were used. The inferential statistics helped in linking data to specific questions by analysing
1144 variables under each objective and make predictions. The data was first tested for normality using
1145 the Shapiro-Wilk test and determined whether to use parametric (normally distributed) or non-

1146 parametric (not normally distributed) analysis. The assumption was that parametric data can be
1147 modelled by a probability distribution with a set of fixed parameters (Hoskin, 2010). If data were
1148 normally distributed, linear regression or correlation analysis could have been used to understand
1149 the relationship between variables in the same objective, for example, education level and level of
1150 awareness. In addition, simple logistic regression could have been used to further understand the
1151 relationship between nominal dependent variables and independent measurement variables, such
1152 as Likert scale variable.

1153
1154 In this case, non-parametric statistics were used as the data was not normally distributed. The
1155 assumption of non-parametric statistics is that the set parameter on the model might change when
1156 the sample size is increased or more data is collected, the set parameter is not fixed (Cox, 2006).
1157 Spearman rank correlation analysis was used. Spearman rank correlation analysis is usually used
1158 instead of linear regression or correlation analysis when there is worry about normality of data.
1159 Spearman rank correlation was used to test the relationship between ranked variables, or one
1160 ranked variable and one measurement variable. In case of only measurement variable, one variable
1161 such as education level, were converted to a ranked variable and run against measurement variable
1162 such as awareness level on Likert scale. Where needed, both measurement variables were
1163 converted to ranks to ease the analysis.

1164
1165 Keyword-In-Context (KWIC) analysis technique was used to analyse data on responses to open-
1166 ended questions obtained from the household survey. Open-ended responses are string of words
1167 given by respondents about their natural understanding of the subject or a target object (Kronberger
1168 & Wagner, 2000). KWIC analysis technique is ideal for large samples where large data is easily
1169 obtained and analysed without compromising quality. Open responses were captured in a computer

1170 through SPSS software together with quantitative data. The data was then analysed manually
1171 through content analysis, where meaning of statements was captured from frequent words which
1172 appear related in sentences. The responses were then homogenised according to their close
1173 synonyms in context and replacing uncommon expressions with their most frequent synonyms.
1174 Words relevant to the question and stimulus of the research topic were retained and are usually in
1175 reasonable frequencies. According to Kronberger and Wagner (2000), the number of relevant
1176 words rarely exceed 20 regardless of the sample size. Supporting verbs, fillers, and other
1177 expressions not relevant for the research were discarded.

1178
1179 Qualitative data from key informant interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. Content
1180 analysis presents an opportunity to obtain both qualitative and quantitative information from the
1181 data content interview discussions (Nyumba et al., 2018). Field notes were transcribed and
1182 uploaded into a computer. An inductive approach was employed to analyse the data thematically.
1183 The inductive qualitative content analysis is used when there is limited previous research findings
1184 about the topic (Armat, Assarroudi, Rad, Sharifi, & Heydari, 2018). The data was thematically
1185 organised under different themes and sub-themes of various factors being analysed. Thematic
1186 analysis process involves primarily familiarising oneself with the data, then generate codes
1187 according to interesting features of the data in relation to specific objectives. At this point the
1188 researcher does not limit themselves to the number of codes, thus listing all emerging ideas, while
1189 in the process identifying relationships and keywords frequently used. The keywords and
1190 relationships are important indicators for themes. The researcher then searches for themes by
1191 collating codes to generate a thematic map. At this point attention is drawn to recurring ideas and
1192 phrases, and extensive contextual ideas connecting the codes. The next step was to define the

1193 themes and thus creating opportunities to extracting interpretations and draw conclusions from the
1194 data in relation to the objectives of the study.

1195
1196 **3.7 Ethics**

1197 To ensure that the researcher and participants in the study are protected from any harm, ethical
1198 issues in data collection, handling, analysis, and presentation were mandatory. To address ethical
1199 considerations aspect in the study, participation of respondents was voluntary and full consent was
1200 obtained. The researcher provided information and assurance for participants to understand the
1201 implications and to reach a fully informed, considered and freely taken decision about whether (or
1202 not) to participate, without pressure or intimidation. That helped to avoid deception or
1203 exaggeration of the opinions and thus flaw the aims and objectives of the study.

1204
1205 All communications in relation to the study was done with honesty and transparency. The data
1206 acquired from the subjects was handled with utmost care and treated with confidentiality to avoid
1207 misuse and subsequent exposure to unintended parties. During data collection, items like names
1208 or identity card numbers that might identify subjects or participants beyond objectives of the study
1209 were avoided, where happened, was protected, and not disclosed to the third party. Representation
1210 of primary data findings was only for the purposes of the study. All biasedness and misleading
1211 information were avoided. Anonymity and privacy of individuals and organisations taking part in
1212 the research was ensured and participants were informed about their right to withdraw from the
1213 study at any stage whenever they so wish. Their dignity and right to decide was prioritised.

1214
1215 Ethics clearance was obtained from the Office of Research and Development (ORD) of the
1216 University of Botswana (REF: UBR/RES/IRB/SOC/GRAD/393) certifying compliance to ethical
1217 requirements when dealing with human subjects. Finally, the researcher declared that they do not

1218 have affiliation in any forms with the participants as per the sampling methods. Either the
1219 participating individuals or organisations in the study area were not funders or related somehow
1220 with any kind of interests to the researcher thus there was no possibility of conflict of interests for
1221 the researcher.

CHAPTER 4

SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS INFLUENCING LOCAL COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN WILDLIFE CONSERVATION

4. Overview

This chapter assesses socio-cultural factors influencing local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga area of the Okavango Delta, Botswana. These socio-cultural factors are considered most complex entities which enables individuals' ability to embark on an activity, and that ability is one of the drivers or "means" of community participation in natural resources management. Ability comprises a combination of factors such as awareness, experience, knowledge, skills and accessibility to information and financial resources (Hung et al., 2011; Jepson et al., 2013).

4.1 Data analysis

To give a visual summary of data, univariate descriptive analysis was done, and results presented in percentages, pie charts, bar charts and tables. Prior to performing inferential statistics, key underlying assumptions were tested and found not to be tenable like the normality test through Shapiro-Wilk test. The Spearman's rho correlation coefficient (ρ) test, a nonparametric test, of association was used to explore the relationships between variables relating to socio-cultural factors influencing local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives. Also, Pearson Chi-Square test was used to test the association between categorical variables. To analyse and deduct meaning from open-ended responses, Keyword-In-Context (KWIC) analysis technique was used to analyse string data obtained from the household survey.

1245 **4.2 Results**

1246 **4.2.1 Awareness and knowledge of formal conservation processes**

1247 Of all the 248 household heads interviewed, few (24.6%) stated that they have knowledge of
1248 wildlife conservation initiatives already operating within their communities. According to
1249 respondent's perspectives, they listed names of initiatives of which they considered to be wildlife
1250 conservation initiatives. The initiatives listed include: agencies on conservation (1); non-
1251 governmental conservation organisations being Bird-Life Botswana (1), CLAWS conservancy (4),
1252 Elephants Without Borders (1), SAVE Elephants (1) and Eco-exist conservancy (32); research
1253 projects (8); community-based organisations being OCT (7), Bukakhwe Cultural Conservation
1254 Trust (3) and Poolers trust (2); resource conservation campaigns being those against veld fires (4),
1255 deforestation (2), poaching (2); community social groupings in conservation (8); and resources
1256 sustainability use regulations (5) such as seasonal harvesting of thatching grasses.

1257
1258 Of the 61 (24.6%) households heads who agreed to having some knowledge of certain wildlife
1259 conservation initiatives, about 50.8 % of them gave their views towards the initiatives they
1260 mentioned. As to whether they perceive them to be serving according to their expectations. Of the
1261 respondents who gave their views, majority (71%) agreed that "yes" the initiatives serve them
1262 well. These respondents were *pro* the initiatives and gave comments like "*yes it helps*", "*yes, it is*
1263 *better they are doing a good job*", "*yes, as the veld fires have greatly reduced*" and "*yes, they help*
1264 *in terms of raising awareness*". Some respondents (16.1%) were optimistic and opined that the
1265 initiatives are better or partially serve according to their expectations. On contrary, some
1266 respondents (22.6%) could not agree that initiatives might be serving according to their
1267 expectations. Some gave comments like "*not at all, there are few aspects lacking*" and "*Its*

1268 *currently not, it used to*”, directing that to a particular conservation initiative of their knowledge.
 1269 Some respondents (3.2%) criticised initiatives by saying “*they are not useful to us*”.

1270
 1271 When respondents were questioned of their awareness of any community-based organisation in
 1272 their area, the majority of respondents (83.5%) opined that they know of existence of one.
 1273 Additionally, 74.2% of respondents, when asked about a specific conservation strategy, indicated
 1274 that they are aware of the 2014 government-imposed hunting ban on wildlife. On Table 3 below,
 1275 the two awareness variables (in rows) are tabulated against a participation variable (in column),
 1276 which sought to know whether a respondent usually takes part in the management of wildlife in
 1277 their area. On this note, 129 (52%) respondents indicated that “yes” they take part against 102
 1278 (41.1%) who said they do not, and 17 (6.9%) who do it sometimes.

1279
 1280 **Table 3: Participation versus awareness statements (existence of CBO’s and Hunting ban)**

Awareness statements		Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?			Total	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
Are you aware of the existence of any community-based organisation in your area? (e.g., OCT)	Yes	60.9	32.6	6.5	184	100
	No	26.6	65.6	7.8	64	100
Are you aware of the 2014 government-imposed “Hunting ban” on wildlife?	Yes	57.0	36.7	6.3	207	100
	No	26.8	63.4	9.8	41	100

1281
 1282 The majority, 60.9 % of respondents who said they are aware of the existence of CBO in their area
 1283 were also likely to participate in management of resources (Table 3). Also, 65.6 % who were not
 1284 aware of any CBO did not participate. The trend was also present on the awareness of hunting ban
 1285 variable as about 57 % of the respondents who were aware, also were participating in management
 1286 of wildlife in their area. Most respondents (63.4 %) who were not aware, were not participating

1287 (Table 3). Further, a Pearson Chi-Square test support there is significant association between the
1288 categorical responses to statements, two of awareness against one for participation as in Table 3.
1289 The test gives a Chi-Square value (χ^2) of 12.525 and a p-value of 0.002 for CBO awareness, and
1290 also, χ^2 of 23.445 and p-value of 0.000 for hunting ban awareness variable.

1291

1292

1293 **Figure 7: Respondents' awareness of select wildlife conservation policies**

1294

1295 Figure 7 above shows how respondents answered (in percentages) about their awareness of
1296 specified conservation strategies or policies. The *Okavango Delta Management Plan* (ODMP) was
1297 the strategy known by most respondents (35.9%) compared to others (Figure 7). It was followed
1298 by the *Community-Based Natural Resource Management (CBNRM) policy* of 2007 which was
1299 known to about 25 % of respondents. The least known strategies are the *Wildlife conservation*
1300 *policy* of 1986 with and the *Wildlife policy* of 2013 with 14.9 %. Few respondents (1.6%) stated
1301 that there were other strategies, not listed, that they are aware of.

1302

1303 When presented with a self-implying statement that “*I know a lot about wildlife conservation in*

1304 *my community*”, most of the respondent (34.3%) stated “disagree” as an answer from five possible

1305 answers (five-point Likert’s scale) (Table 4). Many of the respondents (50.8%) agreed (“strongly

1306 agreed” and “agreed”) with the statement compared to 46 % of those who disagreed (“strongly

1307 disagree” and “disagree”), while 3.2 % of respondents were indifferent. For the statement of “*I*

1308 *know how I can participate in wildlife conservation initiatives in my area*”, a similar pattern

1309 occurred. The difference was that 48% of respondents disagreed with the statement, compared to

1310 46.3 % who agreed. On the other statement that “*I am familiar with wildlife conservation*

1311 *initiatives*”, the majority of respondents (65.7%) agreed with the statement compared to 33.5 %

1312 that held a different opinion.

1313

1314

Table 4: Statements on respondents’ awareness of wildlife conservation initiatives

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
• <i>I know a lot about wildlife conservation in my community</i>	49 (19.8)	77 (31.0)	8 (3.2)	85 (34.3)	29 (11.7)
• <i>I know how I can participate in wildlife conservation initiatives in my area</i>	40 (16.1)	75 (30.2)	14 (5.6)	99 (39.9)	20 (8.1)
• <i>I am familiar with wildlife conservation initiatives</i>	57 (23.0)	106 (42.7)	2 (0.8)	59 (23.8)	24 (9.7)
• <i>I initiate contacts with wildlife officials whenever necessary</i>	9 (8.9)	25 (24.8)	3 (3.0)	47 (46.5)	17 (16.8)
• <i>I am fully aware of the issues related to wildlife conservation in my community</i>	7 (6.9)	36 (35.6)	3 (3.0)	47 (46.5)	8 (7.9)
• <i>I keep up with the news regarding wildlife conservation</i>	3 (3.0)	36 (35.6)	0 (0)	51 (50.5)	11 (10.9)
• <i>I receive information about wildlife conservation in my community</i>	3 (3.0)	20 (19.8)	5 (5.0)	62 (61.4)	11 (10.9)
• <i>I have knowledge about wildlife in my area</i>	11 (10.9)	51 (50.5)	2 (2.0)	25 (24.8)	12 (11.9)
• <i>I know about the likely impacts of</i>	10 (9.9)	52 (51.5)	3 (3.0)	27 (26.7)	9 (8.9)

wildlife conservation initiatives in
our livelihoods

•I know a lot about my community	14 (13.9)	47 (46.5)	3 (3.0)	26 (25.7)	11 (10.9)
----------------------------------	-----------	-----------	---------	-----------	-----------

1315 Note: Percentages are reported in parentheses

1316

1317 In general, from both the ten statements (Table 4), the majority of respondents, with total count of
 1318 728 (50.2%) agreed (“strongly agreed” and “agreed”) to the statements compared to count of 680
 1319 (46.8%) for those who disagreed (“strongly disagreed” and “disagree”). To get some inferential
 1320 sense from data, indices were generated on SPSS from respondents’ values on awareness of select
 1321 wildlife conservation strategy variables on Figure 7 and from the first three Likert scale statements
 1322 on Table 4. The indices are averages of values for the variables per observation. Spearman's rank
 1323 correlation coefficient was used to assess monotonic relationship between the variables of
 1324 strategies awareness index and awareness knowledge Likert scale variable index. Analysis gave a
 1325 correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.404 (correlation is significant at $p = 0.01$). This level of ρ implies
 1326 that there is *low positive correlation* between level of awareness on wildlife conservation strategies
 1327 and the way a respondent will answer to a combination of Likert scale statements in *Table 4* above.

1328

1329 **4.2.2 Skills and experience on wildlife conservation initiatives**

1330 The majority (69%) of respondents, indicated that none within their household members possessed
 1331 any skill other than those related to farming implying that livelihoods were therefore strongly
 1332 dependent on farming and natural resources. Thirty one percent of respondents indicated that
 1333 within their households they were members with other skills, besides farming. The skills
 1334 mentioned are diverse and include artisan skills such as plumbing and carpentry, welding, painting,
 1335 auto-mechanic, and bricklaying and plastering. Other vocational skills include fashion designing,
 1336 catering, and hair dressing. These skills are mostly learned or acquired in formal training setup.

1337 Other skills mentioned as being common amongst household members included natural talents
1338 like singing, dancing, and playing football.

1339
1340 Other skills associated with way of life, which are mostly learned at home through observation
1341 and performing routine household chores, such as harvesting thatching grass, fishing, hunting,
1342 gathering, and searching of medicinal plants. Interviewed households' heads also listed skills in
1343 hand crafting including wood carving and basket weaving. Additionally, skills like safari tracking
1344 and guiding, which can be attributed to the location of the community were mentioned to be
1345 possessed by household members. The household members also possessed skills on management,
1346 business, entrepreneurship, and other academic qualifications.

1347
1348 Around 49.2% of households fell under a category of those with monthly cash earnings being
1349 below P500 (Figure 8). That was followed by 33.9 % who earned between P500 and P1500, which
1350 was the second largest category. Few households (1.6%) had their cash earnings being more than
1351 P5,000.00 a month. The remaining proportions of 9.7 % and 5.6 % of households had their monthly
1352 cash earnings being between “P1,500.00 and P3,000.00” and between “P3,000.00 and P5,000.00”
1353 respectively.

1354

1355
 1356 **Figure 8: Categories of households' monthly cash earnings**

1357
 1358 Most respondents (66.5%) were unemployed or not working. A total of 79 respondents were
 1359 empowered somehow, either formally employed (13.3%) or self-employed (18.5%). Only 1.6% of
 1360 respondents indicated that they have retired from their jobs (Figure 9).

1361
 1362 **Figure 9: Category of respondents' occupation statuses**

1363
 1364 There was a relationship between occupation of respondents and the category at which their

1365 monthly cash earnings fell. The occupation of respondent's variable was turned to ordinal, from
 1366 nominal, with the order of values from small to large being "Working", "Self-employed", "Not-
 1367 working" and "Retired". The monotonic relationship, according to Spearman's correlation
 1368 coefficient, between the variables was negative and low ($\rho = -0.414$). This implied that moving
 1369 from households' heads who are working up to those not working, cash earnings tended to go
 1370 down, slightly moving in an opposite direction.

1371
 1372 A comparison, through cross tabulation, between skills variable and participation variable revealed
 1373 that there was an association between skills possessed by respondents and whether they
 1374 participated in wildlife conservation initiatives or not (Table 5). About 59.2 % of respondents who
 1375 were skilled, participated in wildlife management in their area. Most households (71%) had no
 1376 skilled member, and within these households, there was not much difference between those who
 1377 participated (48%) in wildlife management and those who did not (43%), as the remaining 8.1 %
 1378 were doing it sometimes. Most households (53.4 %) who earning below P1,500 per month
 1379 indicated that they participated in management of wildlife. There was no difference in participation
 1380 patterns for households earning more than P1,500 a month (Table 5).

1381
 1382 **Table 5: Participation versus skills possession and monthly income**

		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			Total	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)		
<i>Skills and income variables</i>					n	%
<i>Does any member of your household possess skills other than farming skills?</i>	Skilled	59.2	36.8	4.0	76	100
	Unskilled	48.8	43.1	8.1	172	100
<i>Household monthly income</i>	0 - P500	51.6	40.2	8.2	122	100
	P501 - P1,500	56.0	39.3	4.7	84	100
	P1,501 - P3,000	45.8	45.8	8.4	24	100
	P3,001 - P5,000	42.9	50.0	7.1	14	100

1383

1384 **4.2.3 Education and information accessibility**

1385 Most respondents (85.9%) indicated that they owned mobile phones. The second most common
 1386 communication device amongst households was wireless radio, which about 64.9 % of respondents
 1387 indicated that their households either had access to or owned. Few of the respondents (5.6%) stated
 1388 that they had access to internet connection (Figure 10). Other communication assets included
 1389 television set and newspapers, of which about 26.6 % and 27.0 % of households indicated they
 1390 had access to or owned, respectively.

1391

1392 **Figure 10: Respondents' access to communication assets**

1393

1394 On education level, most respondents (43.5%) had secondary level education (Figure 11). The
 1395 second largest group of respondents (29.8%) had no education or had never gone to school. About
 1396 31 % of respondents received only a primary school education. Few of respondents (5.2%) had a
 1397 tertiary education qualification, while further four percent had done some vocational education.

1398

1399
1400 **Figure 11: Highest education level of respondents'**

1401
1402 An index variable, “Comm_Assets index”, was created from the “access to communication assets”
1403 variables in SPSS. “Comm_Assets index” returns an average of values for every observation from
1404 all the “access to communication assets” variables. Spearman’s rho correlation analysis returned a
1405 correlation coefficient (ρ) of -0.356, which implies that there is low negative correlation between
1406 an index on communication assets and the level of education of the respondents. The access to
1407 “Comm_Assets index” variable had values between 0 and 1, being average for all the “access to
1408 communication assets” variables which each had either 0 and 1 as values (“yes” = 0 and “no” =
1409 1). This means that a respondent with high level of education such as tertiary education, tended to
1410 have access to many communication assets.

1411
1412 **Table 6: Respondents’ education level and participation**

		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			<i>Total</i>	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
<i>Education level of respondents</i>	None	44.6	44.6	10.8	74	100
	Non-formal	66.7	25.0	8.3	12	100

Primary education	48.4	48.4	3.2	31	100
Secondary education	55.6	38.8	5.6	108	100
Vocational education	60.0	40.0	0	10	100
Tertiary education	53.9	38.4	7.7	13	100

1413

1414 Within respondents with a secondary education level, which the majority of respondents (43.5%)
 1415 have, there is a significant difference between those who participated in wildlife management and
 1416 those who did not. Most of the respondents (55.6 %) in this category do participate in conservation,
 1417 with further 5.6 % doing it sometimes (Table 6). Worth noting is that, for all categories of “non-
 1418 formal”, “secondary”, “vocational” and “tertiary”, more respondents were participating compared
 1419 to those who did not. The rest of the categories (none, primary) did not show any difference.

1420

1421 On focus group discussions, to answer the question of “Do local communities take part in wildlife
 1422 conservation initiatives?”, one of the participants answered by saying “... the problem is lack of
 1423 knowledge and understanding on how the initiatives work within the local communities.” When
 1424 discussing the desirability and attractiveness of the initiatives, participants argued that there is lack
 1425 of access to information pertaining to formal procedures of engagement on those initiatives and
 1426 that generally the local communities lack financial and intellectual resources to engage initiatives.
 1427 Participants further opined that there is lack of knowledge within the locals about formal processes
 1428 of natural resources management. The issue of the need for capacity building also came up when
 1429 the groups discussed about their liberty to comment and raise opinions during the meetings, as
 1430 some participants indicated that there is need for people to be trained or taught about the basic
 1431 skills of formal engagement in management processes. Participants emphasised that their ability
 1432 to participate is enabled by knowledge, understanding of the initiatives and all that enables
 1433 motivation and confidence.

1434

1435 **4.2.4 Local practices and their relation to participation in wildlife conservation**

1436 Of all the 248 households’ heads interviewed, the majority (107) or 43.1 % of the respondents
1437 were single or not yet married (Figure 12). Another significant proportion of respondents were
1438 either lawfully married (23%) or cohabiting (22.6%). The remaining proportion were either
1439 divorced (2.4%) or widowed (8.9%).

1440

1441

1442 **Figure 12: Respondents’ marital statuses**

1443

1444 Though the majority (54%) of households were female-headed, there is no significant difference
1445 between these and those which are male-headed. The male-headed households account for the
1446 remaining 46 %. Within the female-headed households, about 1.6 % are *de facto* (male head or
1447 spouse away) and the majority (52.4%) are *de jure* (widowed, never married, divorced, etc). The
1448 modal number of household members is five, with 15.3 % having that number of people. The mean
1449 number was 6.83 and a median of six. The largest household in the population surveyed had 22
1450 members and the smallest had one member. The number of household members variable has a
1451 standard deviation of 3.47 and a variance of 12.01. The majority of households (69.4%) practice

1452 dryland arable farming and depend on it as source of livelihood (Figure 13). On average, each
 1453 household depended on about two sources of income. Second most common sources of livelihood
 1454 were both cattle production (29.8%) and informal employment (29.8%). Informal employment
 1455 included *Ipelegeng* (government transfers through manual work social welfare program), *piece*
 1456 *jobs* and others. Some households do some businesses to boost their sources of income, and about
 1457 24.2 % of households do some small businesses, and few (0.4%) had medium-large businesses.
 1458 About 16.9 % of households had small stock production as source of livelihood.

1459

1460

1461 **Figure 13: Households’ sources of income**

1462

1463 Of all the 248 households surveyed, 21.8 % had at least one of their members being formally
 1464 employed. *Molapo* (flood recession) farming is not common, and only 0.4 % of households
 1465 indicated that they practiced it and had their livelihoods depending on it (Figure 13). Some of the
 1466 respondents (1.2%) also indicated that there are other sources of income they depended on, such
 1467 as remittances, allowances, and government food relief programmes for the needy and disabled.

1468 Most respondents (37.5%) “agreed” to a statement that “*Both men and women are responsible for*
 1469 *wildlife conservation issues in our community*”. Additionally, 21.8 % “strongly agreed” with the
 1470 statement. About 20.6 % were indifferent towards that statement and could not neither agree nor
 1471 disagree. The rest disagreed with the statement, with 12.9 % “disagreeing” and 7.3 % “strongly
 1472 disagreeing”. A Spearman’s rho analysis between the statement and the variable of household size
 1473 showed that there is very high negative correlation ($\rho = -0.912$). This implies households with
 1474 larger number of members tends to believe it is the responsibility of both men and women to
 1475 engage in wildlife conservation. In another analysis, there was negligible correlation ($\rho = -0.091$)
 1476 between the household size and source of income index. “Source of income index” was developed
 1477 from mean of all sources of livelihood per household or observation. Though the correlation
 1478 coefficient is negative, it is very negligible (closer to zero) and cannot be used to make any
 1479 judgement.

1480
 1481 The majority of married (57.9%), single (51.4%), and cohabiting (55.4%) respondents said they
 1482 participated in management of wildlife in their area (Table 7). There is a difference between that
 1483 and those who were married before and are out of marriage. The majority of respondents who were
 1484 once married, either divorced (66.7%) or widowed (59.1%), said they were not participating in
 1485 wildlife management in their area.

1486
 1487 **Table 7: Participation and marital statuses variables**

		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			<i>Total</i>	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)		
				<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	
<i>Marital statuses of respondents</i>	Single	51.4	43.9	4.7	107	100
	Cohabiting	55.4	37.5	7.1	56	100
	Married	57.9	29.8	12.3	57	100
	Divorced	33.3	66.7	0	6	100

Widowed	36.4	59.1	4.5	22	100
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1488

1489 **4.2.5 Cultural norms and values and their influence on participation in wildlife**
 1490 **conservation**

1491 The study site seemed to be culturally diverse, with a variety of local ethnic groups. The majority
 1492 of respondents (50.8%) are of the *Hambukushu* ethnic group. Also, about 32 % of respondents
 1493 indicated that they were of the *Wayei* ethnicity, which makes it the second most common ethnic
 1494 group (Figure 14). There are also significant number of the *Basarwa* (San) ethnicity in the area, as
 1495 about 14 % of the respondents indicated that they are. Also, other ethnic groups present in the area
 1496 were the *Dxeriku* (1.6%) and *Batawana* (0.8%). Some respondents (1.2%) showed that they do not
 1497 fall under any ethnic groups earlier mentioned and identified themselves as *Bakgalagadi* and
 1498 others.

1499

1500

1501 **Figure 14: Proportion of household heads by ethnicity**

1502

1503 Most of the household heads (41.1%) or people interviewed were youth, falling in the age category
 1504 of “21 – 35 years”. The second largest age category is the “36 – 45 years” which accounts for 22.6
 1505 % of the respondents. There was no significant difference between age categories of “46 – 55

1506 years”, “56 – 65 years” and “66 years and above” as they accounted for 10.1 %, 13.3 % and 12.9
 1507 % of respondents respectively (Figure 15).

1508

1509

1510 **Figure 15: Age categories of household heads**

1511

1512 In general, respondents agreed to statements around issues of cultural norms and values, that
 1513 *“There are local rules and taboos relating to wildlife conservation in our community”*, *“Local*
 1514 *rules and taboos are set and enforced by the Kgosi”*, *“There are sanctions for failure to comply*
 1515 *with local rules and taboos on wildlife conservation”* and *“People in this community see wildlife*
 1516 *as having cultural value”* (Table 8). All the statements were positive and had the highest total
 1517 frequencies on “strongly agree” descending to “strongly disagree” (308, 270, 191, 147 and 76) on
 1518 a five-point Likert scale. Worth noting is that the majority of respondents (69%) agreed to the
 1519 statement that *“There are local rules and taboos relating to wildlife conservation in our*
 1520 *community”*.

1521

1522 **Table 8: Statements of cultural norms and values on wildlife conservation**

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
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•There are local rules and taboos relating to wildlife conservation in our community	90 (36.3)	81 (32.7)	34 (13.7)	37 (14.9)	6 (2.4)
•Local rules and taboos are set and enforced by the Kgosi	33 (13.3)	58 (23.4)	81 (32.7)	46 (18.5)	30 (12.1)
•There are sanctions for failure to comply with local rules and taboos on wildlife conservation	29 (11.7)	58 (23.4)	73 (29.4)	51 (20.6)	37 (14.9)
•People in this community see wildlife as having cultural value	156 (62.9)	73 (29.4)	3 (1.2)	13 (5.2)	3 (1.2)
Total	308 (31.0)	270 (27.2)	191 (19.3)	147 (14.8)	76 (7.7)

Note: Percentages are reported in parentheses

1523
1524

1525 Also, important to note is that the majority of respondents were indifferent towards both statements
1526 that “Local rules and taboos are set and enforced by the Kgosi” (32.7%) and “There are sanctions
1527 for failure to comply with local rules and taboos on wildlife conservation” (29.4%) (Table 8). Of
1528 magnitude, 92.3 % of respondents agreed, either “strongly agree” (62.9%) or “agree” (29.4%), to
1529 the statement that “People in this community see wildlife as having cultural value”, with seldom
1530 (7.6%) disagreeing. An index from all the statements on cultural norms and values was generated
1531 to make inferential statistics, analyse the relationship, with other variables. The relationship
1532 between the statements index and the age of respondents was analysed and gave a negligible (-
1533 0.062) Spearman’s correction coefficient value (ρ). This implies that the two variables had an
1534 insignificant negative relationship, and the monotonic association was very poor to make any
1535 judgement.

1536

1537 **Table 9: Respondents’ age categories against participation**

		Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?			Total	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
Age category of the respondent	21 - 35	55.9	38.2	5.9	102	100
	36 - 45	53.6	42.9	3.6	56	100

46 - 55	48.0	48.0	4.0	25	100
56 - 65	39.4	45.5	15.1	33	100
66 and above	53.1	37.5	9.4	32	100

1538

1539 The majority (54.1%) of youthful people, those younger than 45 years, said they participate in
 1540 management of wildlife in their area (Table 9). For respondents older than 46 years, there was not
 1541 much difference between those participating and those who do not. Further, a Pearson Chi-Square
 1542 test shows that there is no significant association between the two variables. The test gives χ^2 value
 1543 of 7.132 and a p-value of 0.522.

1544

1545 **4.3 Discussion**

1546 Results in this chapter indicate that the majority of household's heads lack knowledge on wildlife
 1547 conservation initiatives in their area. Only 24.6 % of all the 248 household heads interviewed are
 1548 slightly knowledgeable about wildlife conservation initiatives within their communities. In
 1549 similarity, it was argued that, factors like lack of knowledge, and others such as high illiteracy
 1550 rates and lack of economic development are inherent in rural areas of Botswana and hinders
 1551 development goals (Arntzen, 2005b). This was further highlighted in the review of the Remote
 1552 Area Development Programme (RADP), a government program targeted to assist communities in
 1553 remote areas who are characterised by abject poverty, limited sources of income and depend on
 1554 deteriorating natural resources (International Poverty Centre, 2005).

1555

1556 Results further indicated that most respondents were likely to be aware of only policy
 1557 implementation strategies that directly affected their local practices such as community-based
 1558 organisations and precisely the 2014 government-imposed hunting ban on wildlife. This was likely
 1559 due to the impacts it had to livelihoods and probably their indigenous knowledge, as hunting

1560 particularly is somewhat way of sustainably using and managing natural resources (Mogomotsi,
1561 Mogomotsi, Gondo, & Madigele, 2018). This level of awareness was contrary to level of
1562 awareness on national policies and strategies, as only less proportions of respondents were
1563 informed in that regard. Low levels of awareness towards policies might be due to lack of skills
1564 and knowledge to participate in such informed wildlife conservation initiatives, thus limiting their
1565 ability, rendering inclusive management of resources undesirable (Jepson et al., 2013; Tosun,
1566 1999).

1567
1568 Most people did not have notable skills beside farming as results indicated that only 31 % of
1569 households had at least one family member who had non-agricultural skills. Skills are generally
1570 crucial in determining “competence” to constructively engage in a particular process (Norris,
1571 Stevens, Pfefferbaum, Wyche, & Pfefferbaum, 2008). Lack of skills can therefore be a barrier to
1572 communities, in their capacity to participate in wildlife conservation initiatives. Also, Mbaiwa
1573 (2003), observed that though local communities in the Okavango Delta had the opportunity and
1574 benefits for engaging in tourism businesses, these CBNRM projects underperformed. The failure
1575 has been attributed to lack of understanding of policy objectives and lack of business skills by
1576 local communities. This lack of skills, particularly “administrative, organisational, management
1577 and entrepreneurial skills” was further reported by Arntzen (2005; pp 36) as a constraint that local
1578 communities in the Okavango Delta face when exploring the potential of CBNRM initiatives.

1579
1580 The results indicated that the majority, 83.1 %, of households had monthly income of less than
1581 P1500 (~ \$130). Further, 49.2 % of households had monthly income of less than P500 (~ \$44).
1582 This implies that about 50 % of surveyed households were living below the poverty datum line of
1583 P915.70 for rural settlements in the rural areas of North-West region, Botswana (Statistics

1584 Botswana, 2015a). This might be due to that, most household heads (66.5%) were not employed.
1585 These results were in alignment with evidence of reported high poverty levels in the Ngamiland
1586 West, at 33.3 % in 2016 (Statistics Botswana, 2018). Rural poverty and high unemployment rates
1587 are likely to impact on capacity of local communities to participate in wildlife conservation.
1588 Participation in projects and administrative structures by informed community members can be
1589 limited or might suffer due to limited human and financial resources as active populations tend to
1590 migrate to neighbouring urban settlements in search of greener pastures (Kimengsi, Azibo, &
1591 Gwan, 2016).

1592
1593 Most household heads (85.9%) surveyed owned mobile phone devices which coincides with
1594 O'Connell et al. (2019), who opined that there is rapid growth of information and communications
1595 technology (ICT) network connection in rural sub-Saharan Africa. Nonetheless, less household
1596 heads (5.6 %) indicated that they had access to internet connection. The results further indicate
1597 that access to communication assets is positively related to level of education. The more household
1598 heads were educated, the more communications assets they were likely to have access to in their
1599 household. About 30 % of household heads had no formal education, and the rest had at least
1600 primary school education. Literature highlights the importance of education and knowledge in
1601 influencing community members to participate in particular initiatives (Zhu, Guan, & Wei, 2016).
1602 Further, Mogome-Ntsatsi & Adeola (1995), opined that education raised environmental awareness
1603 amongst communities. Also, in this study, most of the participants were youth, and about 60 %
1604 were not older than 45 years. Education and age were found by Garekae, Thakadu, & Lepetu
1605 (2017), to influence people's dependence on natural resources as educated and older people were
1606 found to be less dependent on forest resources. A similar observation by Ofoegbu, Chirwa, Francis,
1607 and Babalola, (2017), that local community social attributes including husbandry skills, years

1608 of residence and age of respondents influenced use and participation on management forest
1609 resources. Parker, *et.al.*, (2014), also observed that where population demographics have a
1610 relatively young age majority, it is likely that they have formal education. This may have influence
1611 on how they appreciate importance of participating in conservation and environmental
1612 sustainability.

1613
1614 Most households surveyed were female-headed but there is no significant difference to those which
1615 are male-headed. Large and female-headed households are mostly regarded as vulnerable, and
1616 poorer as they usually own fewer assets (The World Bank, 2015). The largest household in the
1617 study site had 22 members and modal number of household members was five. The study recorded
1618 many household's practicing dryland arable farming and depending on it as source of livelihood.
1619 Arntzen (2005), concluded that in northern Botswana, particularly the Okavango Delta region,
1620 agriculture and public transfers are most important sources of income, and formal employment
1621 opportunities are limited. Further, Arntzen (2005b) noted that, compared to other regions, there is
1622 high dependence on natural resources and that highlighted worthiness of biodiversity to local
1623 communities in the region.

1624
1625 The study site was culturally diverse, with variety of local ethnicities, but respondents showed a
1626 similar pattern on issues of cultural norms and values. In general, respondents in the study stated
1627 that their cultural norms and values somehow influence the protection and conservation of wildlife
1628 and the environment. Other scholars argue that, supporting the findings of this study,
1629 environmental connotations cannot be discussed without attachment to a specific sociocultural
1630 background (Gfeller, 2019). Similarly, Moswete and Thapa (2015), found out that community
1631 cultural perspectives are strongly related to support for community-based ecotourism

1632 development. In areas where social-ecological relationships are analysed in isolation of some
1633 important factors like cultural preferences, concerns usually emanates about challenges of
1634 communities' ability to adapt to a specific phenomenon (Shinn, 2018).

1635

1636 **4.4 Conclusion**

1637 This chapter demonstrates that local communities in the Greater Seronga Area predominantly had
1638 limited knowledge, notable skills and had low levels of awareness to formally engage in wildlife
1639 management strategies. Local communities in the area were mostly poor with large households
1640 and high unemployment rates. That could limit the extent to which local communities would
1641 actively participate in wildlife conservation. Also, majority of household heads were youth and
1642 literate, that combined with cultural norms and values supporting conservation of wildlife makes
1643 local communities to be concerned to participate in management of wildlife. These factors alone
1644 cannot determine the form and extent at which local communities would or would not participate
1645 in any particular project, but rather describes their capabilities or lack of. It is important to analyse
1646 and understand socio-cultural factors that influence the ability of local communities to participate
1647 in management of resources, and interventions for social problems. To that end, we can conclude
1648 that understanding factors of awareness, experience, knowledge, skills, accessibility to
1649 information, and cultural norms and values is important in ensuring success of resource
1650 conservation strategies which incorporate efforts and require approvals of local communities. For
1651 initiatives to achieve their objectives, they need to have positive outputs in developing the
1652 necessary social skills and sought support within communities.

CHAPTER 5

THE INFLUENCE OF FORMAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES ON LOCAL COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN WILDLIFE CONSERVATION

5. Overview

This chapter assesses the influence of formal management strategies on local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga area of the Okavango Delta, Botswana. Management strategies include processes, policies and regulations that provide opportunities for community involvement in participation processes. They provide a platform in the form of channel of communication or link between the local communities and the central or local government. The variables in this chapter include open channel of communication and political opportunities being inclusiveness of administration processes, policies, institutions and organisations. This chapter therefore, assesses local communities' satisfaction towards wildlife conservation issues, support and perceptions of management strategies, sense of belonging and relations with other stakeholders.

5.1 Data analysis

To give visual summary of data, univariate descriptive analysis was done, and results presented in percentages, pie charts, bar charts and tables. Key underlying assumptions were tested and found not to be tenable, such as normality test through Shapiro-Wilk test. The Spearman's rho correlation coefficient (ρ) test, a nonparametric test, of association was used to explore the monotonic relationship between the variables. Also, Pearson Chi-Square test was run to assess the significance of association between variables. Keyword-In-Context (KWIC) analysis technique was used to extract results from open responses obtained from the household survey.

1678 **5.2 Results**

1679 **5.2.1 Channels of communication**

1680 During the household survey, respondents indicated that there were platforms on which they aired
1681 their views and opinions about wildlife conservation issues in their community. The most common
1682 platform was the kgotla meetings addressed by Kgosi (traditional leader), as most respondents
1683 (74.2%) named it as a platform they used (Figure 16). The second most common platform
1684 according to respondents was also kgotla meetings but addressed by government officials (60 %).
1685 Other platforms include visit to government offices (33.1%), meetings by conservation
1686 organisations (15.7%), workshops on conservation (7.7%) and other platforms (2%).

1687

1688

1689 **Figure 16: Platforms for respondents' opinions on wildlife conservation issues**

1690

1691 Results from key informants interviews coincide with those of the household survey and confirms
1692 that the Kgotla is a common platform for various issues about the society. The Kgotla was said to
1693 be leading in bringing people together so that they have access to resources, help to solve conflicts,
1694 and bring people together for various community activities. The kgotla is said to be historically

1695 the government of the community, which dealt with all matters concerning the community
 1696 including land allocation, tax collection, and all other governance issues. Today, the kgotla is
 1697 where people come together to engage on dialogue over different matters of common concern and
 1698 to receive information on issues of governance and development.

1699
 1700 The results from household survey indicated a relationship between platforms for airing views and
 1701 that of participation in wildlife management. For all the platforms, the percentage of respondents
 1702 who agreed that they participate in wildlife management surpass that of those who said they do
 1703 not (Table 10). Furthermore, when respondents were probed on whether they have a platform to
 1704 voluntarily channel their opinions anytime they desire, the majority (63.7%) did not agree to that.
 1705 Only a few 26.3 % agreed that they have free platform to voluntary channel opinions anytime. To
 1706 get some inferential meaning from data, an index was generated from respondents' platforms
 1707 (Figure 16) variables to create a continuous variable. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was
 1708 used to assess monotonic relationship between the index variable and a categorical variable of
 1709 voluntary platform. The analysis gave a correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.474 implying that there is
 1710 *low positive correlation* between the variables.

1711
 1712

Table 10: Communication platforms against participation variables

Platforms for airing views and opinions about wildlife conservation issues	Do you take part in the management of wildlife?			Total	
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
<i>Kgotla meetings by Kgosi</i>	55.4	40.2	4.4	184	100
<i>Kgotla meetings by Gov't officials</i>	52.3	43.6	4.1	149	100
<i>Workshops on conservation</i>	57.9	42.1	0.0	19	100
<i>Meetings by conservation org's</i>	59.0	35.9	5.1	39	100
<i>Visit to gov't offices</i>	57.4	34.1	8.5	82	100
<i>Others</i>	60.0	0.0	40.0	5	100
Yes	70.0	23.3	6.7	90	100

<i>Is there a platform to voluntarily channel your opinions anytime you may desire?</i>	No	41.8	51.2	7.0	158	100
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1713

1714 A cross tabulation between categorical variables of “*Is there a platform to voluntarily channel*
 1715 *your opinions anytime you may desire?*” and “*Is there a platform to voluntarily channel your*
 1716 *opinions anytime you may desire?*” (Table 10). Seventy percent of respondents who indicated that
 1717 they have a free platform to voluntarily air their opinions, also agreed that they participated in
 1718 management of wildlife in their area. Also, 51.2 % of those who said they do not have a voluntary
 1719 platform, also said they do not participate in management of wildlife in their area. Pearson Chi-
 1720 Square test indicated that there was significant association between the variables. The test gave a
 1721 Chi-Square value (χ^2) of 19.668 and a p-value of 0.000.

1722

1723 Of the people who said there is a channel to voluntarily channel opinions any time they desire, 60
 1724 (66.7%) mentioned one, and they engage with village leadership and other groupings in different
 1725 platforms (Table 11). The platforms mentioned included engaging political representatives, either
 1726 councillors or members of parliament, village traditional leadership being the Kgosi or Kgotla
 1727 meetings and even consulting wildlife officials within government departments. Other platforms
 1728 included engaging with village development committee members, calling conservation
 1729 organisations and CBO’s, and even participating in environmental clubs.

1730

1731 **Table 11: Voluntary platforms mentioned by respondents**

<i>Voluntary platform</i>	<i>Times mentioned</i>
<i>Ward councillor</i>	8
<i>Area member of parliament (MP)</i>	6
<i>Village development committee (VDC)</i>	5

<i>Village leadership i.e., Kgosi</i>	16
<i>Kgotla meetings</i>	23
<i>Community based organisation (CBO)</i>	1
<i>Wildlife officers</i>	7
<i>Environmental club</i>	2

1732

1733

1734 **5.2.2 Administration of conservation processes and policies**

1735 When household heads were asked whether they understand the idea on which the CBNRM policy
1736 of 2007 was founded, there was no significant difference between those who agreed and those
1737 disagreeing. About 50.6 % of respondents said they were aware of the premise while the partial
1738 49.2 % said they were not aware. When probed further, 60 % of those who were aware of the
1739 premise on which the CBNRM policy of 2007 was founded, opined that they thought the policy
1740 was helping or achieving the objective it was set for. The other 40 % felt the policy was not
1741 performing to its full potential. Relating the CBNRM policy objectivity to participation, most
1742 respondents (67.8%) who thought the policy was succeeding, said they were also actively
1743 participating in the management of wildlife in their area (Table 12). About 53.6 % of those who
1744 thought the CBNRM policy was not achieving its objectives, were also actively participating in
1745 management of wildlife. Generally, most respondents who gave their views about the policy were
1746 actively participating in management of wildlife. Worth noting is how respondents who were not
1747 actively participating in management of wildlife in the area reacted to the question. Only 27.4 %
1748 of respondents who were in support of the CBNRM policy did not participate compared to 41.1 %
1749 of those who felt the policy was failing.

1750

1751 **Table 12: CBNRM policy objectivity and hunting ban awareness, against participation**

		Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?			Total	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
Do you think the CBNRM policy is helping or achieving the objective it was set for?	Yes	67.8	27.4	4.8	84	100
	No	53.6	41.1	5.3	56	100
Are you aware of the 2014 government-imposed "Hunting ban" on wildlife?	Yes	60.9	32.6	6.5	184	100
	No	26.6	65.6	7.8	64	100

1752

1753 When respondents were asked to give their views over the CBNRM policy, few of the respondents

1754 (31.2%) who were aware of the policy acceded. Most of the respondents (59%) were undoubtedly

1755 in support of initiatives due from the policy. These respondents stated that the CBNRM is a “good”

1756 policy, opining that, it helps communities to have a stake in resources around them through benefits

1757 of employments and improved livelihoods. The policy was commended for enabling communities

1758 to view conservation with a better and positive perspective. Amid positive comments, other

1759 respondents (10.3%) also decried lack of leadership capacities from amongst local communities to

1760 implement and manage the initiatives borne out of the policy. Furthermore, respondents felt though

1761 the policy was poorly implemented, had potential to improve locals participation in conservation.

1762

1763 Some of the respondents (7.7%) were too distant to grasp the context of the policy as they

1764 perceived it as an instrument for people who are well informed and also opined that the procedure

1765 to engage and implement the policy is difficult for local communities. Respondents (15.4%) also

1766 felt the community in general needed to be capacitated to take their role within natural resource

1767 management through the policy. They stated that they needed to be informed about the policy and

1768 be given all powers and independence in management and use of resources in their area.

1769 Furthermore, some (25.6%) opined that the policy implementation and management is not good

1770 enough in the area. They mentioned setbacks such as lack of monitoring, poor leadership, and
1771 maladministration in organisations (CBOs) and poor implementation of projects.

1772

1773 Most of the respondents (72%) agreed that they are aware of the 2014 government-imposed
1774 “Hunting ban” on wildlife. Only few respondents 25.8 % indicated that they did not have any
1775 knowledge of the ban. A cross tabulation shows that there was relationship between a variable of
1776 hunting ban awareness and one on participation in management of wildlife in the area (Table 12).

1777 Most respondents (60.9%) who were aware of the hunting ban, also opined that they actively
1778 participated in wildlife management. Similarly, 65.6 % of those who were not aware, were also
1779 not participating. Further, a Pearson Chi-Square test indicated a significant association between
1780 the variables of hunting ban awareness and participation. The test gave a Chi-Square value (χ^2) of
1781 23.445 and a p-value of 0.000.

1782

1783 The respondents were further asked on how the 2014 government-imposed hunting ban on wildlife
1784 affected their conservation efforts. About 31% of consenting respondents gave their views that the
1785 ban came as a surprise move. Some of respondents (13%) were positive towards it and indicated
1786 that it was a good initiative that had helped improve wildlife populations in the area. On the other
1787 hand, some respondents (18.5%) did not appreciate the ban. They acknowledged the increase in
1788 wildlife populations and attributed that to increasing human-elephant conflict and damage of
1789 vegetation due to overpopulation of elephants. This proportion of respondents further indicated
1790 that the ban was a setback to their conservation efforts in many aspects, more so that they
1791 considered hunting as a way to benefit from wildlife and cultural conservation strategy.

1792

1793 **5.2.3 Affiliation to community groups and associations**

1794 The majority, about 75 %, of respondents were not affiliated to any organisation in their respective
 1795 villages. Of the 62 (25%) that said they were affiliated to organisations, 55 (88.7% of them) gave
 1796 examples of organisations or groupings they are members of. The table below (Table 13) shows
 1797 examples of organisations and frequencies or number of times per types of groupings as they were
 1798 mentioned by respondents during household survey.

1799
 1800 **Table 13: Type of organisations and number of times mentioned**

<i>Grouping/ Organisation type</i>	<i>Times mentioned</i>	<i>Examples</i>
<i>Conservation clubs</i>	16	Eco-Adult club, Eyes-On-The-Delta, PACT Club, HATAB, Environmental education Club
<i>Religious groups</i>	4	Churches
<i>Cultural groups</i>	13	BoKhakhwe, Thinarungana, Zikhanga, Kita Shame, Moshova and Mphera cultural groups
<i>Development committees</i>	5	Village development committee (VDC), Farmers committee
<i>Associations</i>	5	Parents-Teachers Association (PTA), Fisheries Club, Guide Association
<i>Social clubs</i>	7	Phuthatswana, Sebatana choirs, Fokotsa Dino, Gugubese Youth Group
<i>Sports clubs</i>	2	Football clubs
<i>Community-based organisation</i>	9	Makgobokgobo Trust, Okavango Community Trust (OCT)

1801
 1802 Of the organisations mentioned, 72 % were concerned with wildlife conservation (Figure 17). The
 1803 other 15 % of the groupings were not concerned with wildlife conservation, and the remaining 13

1804 % were concerned with environmental issues to some extent. On opinion uptake, about 78 % of
1805 those who were members or somehow engaged in organisations felt that their opinions were
1806 appreciated during decision-making. Only 15 % could not agree to that and the remaining 6.7 %
1807 were indifferent, saying their opinions were seldom considered. Those who agreed to that were
1808 also satisfied, as about 74.6 % said they were satisfied with the level of community opinion uptake
1809 in their organisations' decision-making processes.

1810
1811 **Figure 17: Organisations concerned with wildlife conservation**

1812
1813 Respondents who are registered members of organisations were most likely to take part in wildlife
1814 management. About 69.4% of the respondents who were registered members agreed that they do
1815 participate in wildlife management (Table 14). Of respondents who were not active in
1816 organisations, there was no significant difference between those who participated in wildlife
1817 management (46.2%) and those who did not (45.7%). The remaining proportion (8.1%) were those
1818 who did it sometimes. Pearson Chi-Square test indicated an association between organisation
1819 membership and participation in wildlife management. The test gave a Chi-Square value (χ^2) of
1820 10.144 and a p-value of 0.006.

1821

1822 **Table 14: Respondents’ organisation membership against participation**

		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			<i>Total</i>	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Are you or any member of your household, registered member of any community organisation in the village?</i>	Yes	69.4	27.4	3.2	62	100
	No	46.2	45.7	8.1	186	100

1823

1824 Most respondents (83.5%) were aware of existence of community-based organisations (CBO) in

1825 their respective villages. Almost all the respondents acknowledged that they shared the CBOs with

1826 their neighbouring villages or communities and there were challenges arising from same CBO’s.

1827 About 31.5 % of respondents said they encountered challenges with their CBO’s, the majority of

1828 which arose from sharing the organisation with other villages. The challenges of the CBO’s

1829 mirrored around allocation and management of resources, either economic or social. More

1830 grievances arose from the way resources were allocated in the CBOs mentioned. The distribution

1831 of resources was mentioned for about 37 times by respondents during the household survey. These

1832 respondents labelled the allocation of resources as unfair, uneven, improper, and mostly done with

1833 elements of jealousy and discrimination. The resources were considered as benefits which are

1834 unfairly distributed in the community and thus creating conflict.

1835

1836 Further, challenges related to administration of CBO’s were mentioned 19 times by respondents.

1837 The challenges included poor administration, corruption, and lack of transparency. Also, lack of

1838 representation, particularly in decision making and important events, lack of inclusiveness and

1839 poor consultation on boards and decisions by some sections of the community were also some of

1840 the administrative setbacks mentioned. The act of unfairness, which respondents consider to be

1841 problematic, was also said to be prevalent in the appointment of staff or board members in the

1842 organisations. About 29 % (18/62) of respondents who were associated to certain organisations
 1843 mentioned favouritism, nepotism, bias as a concern in hiring of staff within the communities. The
 1844 discrimination and other unfair treatment, though not important to this study, were even mentioned
 1845 along village and tribal lines, and, for some rare instance, family lines.

1846
 1847 Most of respondents agreed (“agreed” and “strongly agreed”) to statements related to role of both
 1848 local leaders and government in management of natural resources in their area (Table 15). A
 1849 cumulative 83.1 %, 61.3 %, 94 % and 76.6 % of respondents agreed (total of “strongly agreed”
 1850 and “agreed”) to statements that “*Traditional leaders (Chiefs and elders) have an important role*
 1851 *to play in wildlife conservation*”, “*A mix of cultural and government wildlife management*
 1852 *strategies are crucial in light of high and persistent human-wildlife conflict*”, “*Government should*
 1853 *be responsible for all the compensation for losses and damages caused by wildlife*” and
 1854 “*Government should allow communities to impose their rules on conservation of wildlife in their*
 1855 *area*” respectively. On contrary, about 69 % of respondents either “disagreed” or “strongly
 1856 disagreed” to the statement that “*Government should let people use wildlife as much as they might*
 1857 *need*”.

1858
 1859 **Table 15: Respondents’ perceptions on role of local leadership in wildlife conservation**

<i>Statements</i>	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
• <i>Traditional leaders (Chiefs and elders) have an important role to play in wildlife conservation</i>	112 (45.2)	94 (37.9)	23 (9.3)	13 (5.2)	6 (2.4)
• <i>A mix of cultural and government wildlife management strategies are crucial in light of high and persistent human-wildlife conflict</i>	55 (22.2)	97 (39.1)	48 (19.4)	28 (11.3)	20 (8.1)
• <i>Government should be responsible for all the compensation for losses and damages caused by wildlife</i>	147 (59.3)	86 (34.7)	5 (2.0)	8 (3.2)	2 (0.8)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Government should allow communities to impose their rules on conservation of wildlife in their area 	100 (40.3)	90 (36.3)	11 (4.4)	33 (13.3)	14 (5.6)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Government should let people use wildlife as much as they might need 	37 (14.9)	30 (12.1)	10 (4.0)	110 (44.4)	61 (24.6)

1860 *Note: Percentages are reported in parentheses*

1861

1862 **5.2.4 Perceptions of participation levels in wildlife conservation**

1863 Most respondents (57.7%) indicated that the community was generally consulted by central
 1864 government officials on decision-making processes of wildlife conservation. Also, worth noting is
 1865 that about 37.5 % of surveyed household heads felt locals were just being informed of decisions
 1866 taken on wildlife management in their area (Figure 18). Also, about 9.3 % of respondents opined
 1867 that local communities were leading the decision-making processes on wildlife conservation.

1868

1869

1870 **Figure 18: Perception of the form of participation in decision-making**

1871

1872 Further, 6.9 % of respondents felt local communities were being told of possible solutions to a
 1873 problem and about 4.4 % opining that there was no relationship between locals and government in

1874 decision-making processes (Figure 18). A cross-comparison between perception of participation
 1875 form and whether respondents thought they were participating in wildlife management or not
 1876 illustrates that majority of respondents who felt locals were leading the decision-making processes
 1877 (56.5%) and those who felt there is only consultation (56.6%) were also participating in those
 1878 processes (Table 16). Most respondents who opined that there were informed (48.4%) of decisions
 1879 in wildlife management processes and those who opined there were no relationship between
 1880 government and local communities (54.5%), were also participating in management of wildlife in
 1881 their area.

1882
 1883 **Table 16: Perceived levels of participation and respondent’s participation**

		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			<i>Total</i>	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
<i>Participation levels in decision-making processes on wildlife conservation</i>	Citizen power	56.5	30.4	13.0	23	100
	Consultation	56.6	37.1	6.3	143	100
	Informing	48.4	45.2	6.5	93	100
	Told of solutions	41.2	52.9	5.9	17	100
	No relationship	54.5	18.2	27.3	11	100
	Other	0	100	0	2	100

1884
 1885 Though some respondents felt there was no relationship between government and the local
 1886 communities in the management of wildlife, the majority (54.5%) of them indicated that they
 1887 participated in available wildlife management platforms in their area. The majority (52.9%) of
 1888 respondents who opined that local communities are only being told of possible solutions, were not
 1889 participating in management of wildlife in the area. A Pearson Chi-Square test indicated an
 1890 insignificant association between the variables of participation level and participation with
 1891 exception of variable on “no relationship”. The test gave a Chi-Square value (χ^2) of 2.220 and a

1892 p-value of 0.330 for “citizen control” variable and consequently for “consultation” ($\chi^2 = 2.903$, p
1893 = 0.234), “informing” ($\chi^2 = 1.000$, p = 0.606), “told of solutions” ($\chi^2 = 1.057$, p = 0.590), and
1894 “other” ($\chi^2 = 2.886$, p = 0.236). For “no relationship” variable, the test gave a Chi-Square value
1895 (χ^2) of 8.488 and a p-value of 0.014. Further, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient test indicated
1896 that there is negligible correlation between the participation level variables of “no relationship”
1897 and participation. The monotonic relationship assessment gave a correlation coefficient (ρ) of -
1898 0.031.

1899
1900 From the focus group discussions, participants engaged on a voting process to illustrate their
1901 perceived current levels of community participation and a scenario for a desired level of
1902 participation in their area. Out of a total of 87 votes from five groups, 56.3 % voted for passive
1903 participation implying that they are being informed of decisions (Figure 19). Consultative
1904 participation was voted with 18.4 %, involvement with 9.2 % of the votes, collaborative
1905 participation with 11.5 % and empowerment with 4.6 %. The participants discussed reasons for
1906 their selection. The reasons advanced by group participants on why they think there is currently
1907 informing includes that the government just brings initiatives to them and there are a lot of
1908 instances where they were being told or given directives. One participant opined that “mostly we
1909 are given directives by government of what is to be done, for example the hunting ban which was
1910 done without consulting us. All the consequences of the hunting ban are faced by us here.” The
1911 other saying “we always talk but there is nothing coming out of it.” It was evident from the
1912 discussions that occasionally the local communities were consulted though one participant said,
1913 “the consultations are not genuine enough, the officials always come with directives where we are
1914 told of what is going to happen, our voices are not heard but we always talk when we get a chance.”

1915

1916

1917 **Figure 19: Focus groups' perceived and desired participation levels**

1918

1919 For the desired level of community participation, only 1.1 % voted for a passive participation type

1920 out of 87 votes (Figure 19). Around 2.3 % voted for consultation, 17.2 for involvement and 23 %

1921 for collaborative participation. Most of the votes were on empowerment, as 56.3 % indicated that

1922 they need a situation where the local communities have the power over the management of wildlife.

1923 They were reasons supporting the desire for an interactive participation and they included that

1924 local communities must be empowered so they lead and are in agreement before anything can be

1925 done, and also for them to benefit from their resources. One participant commented that “we are

1926 the one facing the consequences and who knows our situation better which means we are to be the

1927 once making certain decisions concerning the issues of human-wildlife conflict.” The group

1928 participants engaged on robust discussions illustrating the need for local communities to be at the

1929 forefront of decision-making processes concerning management of resources in their area. The

1930 other participant from one of the groups opined that “we want collaboration and empowerment as

1931 locals, in that instance we are able to bring ideas together, lead the discussions and

1932 implementations of our ideas; it is easier to follow and observe rules and regulations made and
1933 formulated by us rather than ones made by someone else.”

1934

1935 **5.3 Discussion**

1936 This chapter has demonstrated that local communities had platforms for airing their views and
1937 opinions about wildlife conservation issues. The results also indicated that most common platforms
1938 are the traditional systems like Kgotla meetings. The Kgotla, as a local traditional institution,
1939 serves effectively as a channel of communication between the local communities and policy
1940 makers, or government but without having any legitimacy on management of resources. The
1941 traditional systems and institutions due to their non-inclusive and informal culture have, since
1942 introduction of colonial rules, lost control and legitimacy over natural resources management
1943 (Agarwal, 2001; Thakadu, 2005). This can bring a gap in knowledge sharing and dialogue over
1944 area specific policy issues. To support this assertion, Sinha and Singh (2011), when assessing
1945 community forest management institutions in India, concluded that local communities may be
1946 subjected to missing opportunities for uplifting their livelihoods through resource use because of
1947 communication gap between them and policy makers.

1948

1949 Results further illustrates that mostly local communities do not have access to platforms to
1950 voluntarily channel their opinions anytime they may desire as terms of engagement are dictated by
1951 the government and not by the local or traditional leadership. This can also hinder the ability of
1952 local communities to explore possible opportunities to engage in wildlife management. Also, local
1953 communities might be hindered to sustainably use or conserve wildlife in their area, and even
1954 accessing other avenues to better their welfare. In this study, the results indicated that local

1955 communities were generally not aware (with exception of few) of the CBNRM policy of 2007.
1956 Further, the few that were aware, did not know the premise on which the policy was founded. The
1957 CBNRM policy of 2007 was founded on the premise of promoting and empowering local
1958 communities on economic and social development through resources use and conservation
1959 (Arntzen et al., 2003; Government of Botswana, 2008; Mbaiwa & Stronza, 2010).

1960
1961 Policies in conservation give local communities legitimate opportunity to actively participate in
1962 wildlife conservation. According to Roe, Nelson, and Sandbrook (2009; 51), “policies are
1963 effectively a statement of government’s intentions, strategy, and overall vision ...”. Good policies
1964 and institutions through options of rights, access to information and community involvement in
1965 decision making enables optimal and sustainable wildlife use and conservation by local
1966 communities (Roe, Jones, Bond, & Bhatt, 2006). Participation of local communities can be
1967 hindered by a variety of factors including “lack of supporting national policy” amongst others
1968 (Roe, Nelson, & Sandbrook, 2009). Where there are policies like CBNRM policy in Botswana,
1969 there are challenges facing the implementation of projects and processes, and they include lack of
1970 knowledge, problematic stakeholder relations, and restrictions related to tourism (Hara, Turner,
1971 Haller, & Matose, 2009). All those are attributed to poor participation of local communities in
1972 natural resource management.

1973
1974 The results indicated that most of the local communities in the study area were knowledgeable and
1975 aware of the 2014 government-imposed hunting ban on wildlife. This might be due to the impact
1976 the hunting ban had on livelihoods of communities in northern Botswana, and specifically around
1977 the Okavango Delta, Chobe and Makgadikgadi areas (Mbaiwa, 2018; Mogomotsi et al., 2018).
1978 Upon its start, CBNRM programmes initially had safari hunting as the main income generating

1979 activity (Mbaiwa, 2015, 2018). Therefore, results of this study corroborate assertions by Mbaiwa
1980 (2018) that the hunting ban negatively affected livelihoods of communities in wildlife areas, being,
1981 loss of income for Trusts and loss of jobs by individuals previously working for safari hunting
1982 operations. These would mean that the ban touched lives of many people and thus the awareness.
1983 Also, the consultations made by government prior to implementation of the ban contributed to the
1984 awareness levels amongst local communities and other stakeholders in wildlife areas. The
1985 consultations were made through Kgotla meetings and workshops with the public (Mbaiwa, 2018).
1986
1987 Further, results indicated that most community members are neither affiliated nor registered
1988 members of conservation organisations in their area. Being a member of an organisation gives an
1989 individual opportunity to be part of local community structures for management and allocation of
1990 resources. Membership to groups and organisations means participants or members act together
1991 for a common goal, and that is social capital (Petruzzi, Busquets, & Pitt, 2015), which gives access
1992 to legitimate allocation of common resources (Mosimane & Aribeb, 2005; Poteete, 2009). The
1993 ability of a community to collectively work together in groups implies there is social capital, results
1994 on this study indicated otherwise, that there is limited social capital in the area. Self-organisation
1995 of local communities into groups, which is social capital as highlighted in the conceptual
1996 framework of this study, may empower them to easily resolve problems, or realise benefits from
1997 collective action amid differences and challenges (Petruzzi et al., 2015), and more easily if guided
1998 by constitutional policy (Go, Trunfio, & Della-Lucia, 2013).
1999
2000 In this case, the constitutional policy, being the CBNRM, enabled communities to establish CBO's
2001 not only in the study area. The establishment of CBO's, locally referred to as "Trusts", was mainly
2002 for the purpose of empowering local communities in making decisions on the use and management

2003 of natural resources around them (Moswete & Thapa, 2018; Thakadu, 2005). In that regard, results
2004 indicated that most of local communities were aware of existence of CBOs in their respective
2005 villages. The high level of awareness might be influenced by importance of the role played by
2006 CBOs in uplifting economic wellbeing of local communities. The CBO's mostly aim to provide
2007 economic benefits to constituents through employment, poverty alleviation and other development
2008 projects (Mbaiwa & Stronza, 2010). The upliftment of livelihoods does not directly translate to
2009 engagement in management of resources. Though well known, these CBNRM initiatives are being
2010 criticized for undermining and not substantially empowering local communities in their
2011 administration and decision-making, examples being the "trusts" in Botswana and "WMAs" in
2012 Tanzania (Cassidy, 2020; Kicheleri, Mangewa, Nielsen, Kajembe, & Treue, 2021; Kicheleri,
2013 Treue, Nielsen, Kajembe, & Mombo, 2018).

2014
2015 According to results on this chapter, community participation in the study area has been
2016 characterised as consultation on decisions to be taken or merely informing. Assessing earlier
2017 studies, and the level of awareness realised within communities in this study, it is questionable
2018 whether the local communities are consulted or are just being informed of decisions taken. For
2019 example, Blackie (2019) and Mbaiwa (2018) found out that processes leading to the
2020 implementation of the hunting ban were more centralised and came as a government policy
2021 directive. Further, the studies went on to label the processes as consultative, adding that concerned
2022 parties like local communities, safari hunting tour operators and even scholars were consulted prior
2023 to the introduction of the hunting ban through workshops and public meetings (Blackie, 2019;
2024 Mbaiwa, 2018).

2025

2026 **5.4 Conclusion**

2027 There are local platforms that serves as modes on which communities can participate in
2028 management of resources around then. These modes are in form of local organisations and
2029 institutions. Management strategies have an influence on local community participation in wildlife
2030 conservation initiatives. Nonetheless, the management strategies in the Greater Seronga Area were
2031 not influential enough, as they were mainly consultative platforms, to enhance active participation
2032 of communities in wildlife conservation. Consultation does not guarantee the majority or
2033 community power in management of resources but rather much better opportunity to have a say
2034 on decision-making. It is clear from this chapter that the said modes have no power or legitimacy
2035 over resources and the processes are largely centred around the central government. There was
2036 less knowledge and awareness of formal procedures on community participation and involvement
2037 like the CBNRM policy. It is concluded in this chapter that participation of local communities in
2038 management of wildlife was poor, and processes were centrally controlled by government. Local
2039 communities centred conservation approaches are endorsed in the Greater Seronga Area as they
2040 are largely legitimate and well placed in dealing with conservation conflicts and guaranteeing
2041 support of communities. Participatory approaches give communities the opportunity to raise
2042 opinion, have power in decision making, and holding rights to sustainably use resources. The
2043 effectiveness and quality of the participatory approaches shape community perceptions towards
2044 resources. Communities' views towards natural resource management strategies therefore
2045 influence how they will voluntarily be involved and consequently influence the outcomes of the
2046 same strategies.

2047 **CHAPTER 6**

2048 **THE INFLUENCE OF HOUSEHOLD ECONOMIC TRADEOFFS ON LOCAL COMMUNITY**

2049 **PARTICIPATION IN WILDLIFE CONSERVATION**

2050 **6. Overview**

2051 This chapter assesses the influence of household economic trade-offs on local community
2052 participation in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga Area of the Okavango
2053 Delta, Botswana. Individuals' choices to participate depends on availability of benefits, and these
2054 perceived benefits are their motivation. Motivation is an important factor in driving individual's
2055 decision to participate in a process. It can affect the intensity and direction of the behaviour of
2056 decision making. The economic trade-offs are derived from the residuals of costs and benefits and
2057 the variables include, a) identified responsibilities, b) perceived personal benefits, c) value
2058 associated with resources, and d) the costs of living alongside wildlife. Therefore, this chapter
2059 assesses the relationship between benefits and costs as factors influencing motivation of local
2060 communities' participation in wildlife conservation initiatives.

2061 **6.1 Data analysis**

2062 **6.1 Data analysis**

2063 To give visual summary of data, univariate descriptive analysis was done, and results presented in
2064 percentages, pie charts, bar charts and tables. Prior to performing inferential statistics, key
2065 underlying assumptions were tested and found not to be tenable, like the normality test through
2066 Shapiro-Wilk test. The Spearman's rho correlation coefficient (ρ) test, a nonparametric test, of
2067 association was used to explore the relationships between variables relating to socio-cultural
2068 factors influencing local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives. To obtain
2069 frequencies and meaning of open-ended responses from household survey data, Keyword-In-
2070 Context (KWIC) analysis technique was used.

2071 **6.2 Results**

2072 **6.2.1 The costs of living alongside wildlife**

2073 Communities in the study area incurred some costs on proceeds for livelihoods due to the presence
2074 of wildlife in their vicinity. Household survey results indicated that the majority of respondents
2075 (68.5%) were affected by crop raiding, specifically by elephants and other wild animals (Figure
2076 20). Secondly, 35.5 % (88) of the respondents showed that their farming activities were affected
2077 by livestock predation by wild carnivores such as lions, hyenas, cheetahs, crocodiles and so on.
2078 About 38 (15.3%) respondents indicated that they were threatened by droughts. Other threats
2079 included natural disasters (5.2%), stock theft (4.8%), veld fires (1.6%) and others (6.9%) like crop
2080 raiding by cattle, loss of stock and harvest due to pests or diseases.

2081

2082

2083 **Figure 20: Threats to households' farming activities**

2084

2085 To mitigate, prevent and manage the threats, households put some measures in place. Measures

2086

put in place against crop raiding, particularly by wild animals included the use of noisy materials

2087 (scrap cans, metal sheet pieces) on fencing, which was used by 57.7 % of the respondents (Figure
 2088 21a). About 32.7% of the respondents also reported that they used chilli pepper to deter elephants
 2089 from their crops. Other measures included guarding the fields at night (16.1%), while others (6.5%)
 2090 either did nothing, or made some fires at night, while none used electric fences.

2091

2092

2093 **Figure 21: Measures against crop raiding (a) and livestock predation (b) by wildlife**

2094

2095 The measures against livestock predation included kraaling at night (34.7%), moving livestock
 2096 during peak seasons (3.2%), herding (1.6%), use of livestock guarding dogs (0.8%) and other
 2097 measures (1.6%) (Figure 21b). Of the respondents who experienced damage caused by wildlife,
 2098 some received compensation for either livestock predation or crop raiding. For livestock predation,
 2099 about 47.9 % of the respondents said they once received some compensation. Still on livestock
 2100 predation, 33 % stated that they did not receive any compensation and 19.1 % said they received
 2101 it sometimes (Figure 22a). On crop raiding, the majority of respondents (51.2%) said they did not
 2102 receive compensation, while 32.9 % received it and 15.9 % also received it at some point in time
 2103 (Figure 22b).

2104

2105 **Figure 22: Compensation for both livestock predation (a) and crop raiding (b) by wildlife**

2106

2107 About 65 (26.2%) of the respondents complained about the compensation programme. Most of the
 2108 respondents (52.3%) who complained said “*it takes too long*” for them to receive their
 2109 compensation after reporting to government officials. The longest waiting period reported during
 2110 the household survey was up to five years. Also, the respondents (36.9%) indicated that they
 2111 always report their cases to the relevant department offices, but the officials never show up to
 2112 assess the damage done by wildlife. In case of no assessment, the victim receives no compensation.
 2113 In other instances, the respondents (7.7%) said they never reported incidences of predation or crop
 2114 raiding by wildlife because they did not see the value of doing so. Further, saying (3.1%) that the
 2115 compensation was not reliable nor useful.

2116

2117 Results from the household survey indicated that the majority of the respondents were not satisfied
 2118 with the compensation received for damages of household agricultural properties caused by
 2119 wildlife. About 77.6 % of the respondents indicated that they were not satisfied with compensation

2120 for livestock predation and 86.3 % for crop damages. About 19 % of the respondents who received
2121 compensation for livestock predation said they were satisfied, compared to only 8.8 % who were
2122 satisfied with compensation for crop damages. Further, 3.4 % and 5.0 % were satisfied to some
2123 extent by compensation for livestock predation and crop damages, respectively (Figure 23).

2124

2125

2126 **Figure 23: Satisfaction on compensation for livestock predation (a) and crop damage (b)**

2127

2128 Results from the household survey indicated that respondents experienced some limitations in
2129 accessing some natural resources for household use. About 31.0 % (77) of the respondents
2130 indicated that they had challenges in accessing aquatic resources, for example fish, reeds, edible
2131 plants, and others (Figure 24). Also, 30.2 % (75) of the respondents experienced limitations in
2132 accessing forage or range resources including firewood, fibre, and thatching grasses, for household
2133 uses. It was also indicated that land was not easy to access in the study area as about 24.2 % (60)
2134 indicated that they had limitations in accessing it for various purposes. To some extent, there were
2135 some limitations on accessing water such as for livestock, irrigation purposes, as about 5.6 % (14)
2136 of the respondents indicated that there are some challenges.

2137

2138 **Figure 24: Resources access limitations**

2139

2140 Further, about 10.1 % (25) of the respondents commented on how the limitations affected their

2141 household livelihood activities. Some respondents mentioned that, because of unfavourable laws

2142 in place, they are not allowed burn old grasses, therefore they attributed that to be the cause of

2143 drought on livestock as they had to feed on old and unpalatable grasses. Further, some respondents

2144 opined those restrictions and regulations in place prevent them from harvesting enough thatching

2145 grass to satisfy their needs. Also, respondents indicated that it is difficult for them to acquire

2146 licences to harvest forest and range resources (i.e., thatching grass, reeds etc) for household uses.

2147 On land, respondents (20%) said that it takes long to be allocated agricultural land by the land

2148 authorities, consequently demoralising communities, particularly youth to engage in farming

2149 activities. All the limitations on accessing resources, particularly aquatic resources (i.e., fish, reeds,

2150 edible plants etc) have been attributed to loss of household income opportunities and loss of

2151 nutritional supply. Though the respondents stated that they had access to various natural resources

2152 in their area, they still decried lack of market for products derived.

2153

2154 As mentioned earlier in chapter four of this thesis, the majority, 184 (72%) of respondents said
2155 that they were aware of the 2014 government-imposed hunting ban on all wildlife. Some
2156 respondents gave their views about how the ban affected their conservation efforts. When
2157 respondents were further questioned about the impacts of the “Hunting ban” law on their
2158 household livelihoods, as an example of the wildlife management strategy, 31% (57) of them gave
2159 differing views. Respondents opined that the shutdown of safari hunting operations resulted in loss
2160 of jobs (54.4 % of those who gave views) and consequently loss of income to sustain livelihoods.
2161 The ban affected livelihoods activities either directly or indirectly, as respondents showed that it
2162 led to reduction in livelihood means (14%), hindering diversification. As a result, the ban was also
2163 attributed to the increase in poverty levels amongst households as some were dependent on hunting
2164 activities. The respondents (19%) also mentioned loss of free meat from safari hunters, which is
2165 also a disadvantage to households who used to receive the fresh meat and now are in poverty.

2166
2167 Other respondents (7%) opined that the hunting ban did not only impact livelihoods at household
2168 level, but at community level as people lost some economic activities. The hunting ban led to loss
2169 of opportunities in wildlife trophy trading businesses by community-based organisations. Some
2170 respondents (19.3%) mentioned increase in human-wildlife conflict incidences, being damage to
2171 household assets, damage to crops, predation of livestock and even loss of human lives. This was
2172 mainly attributed to an increase in wildlife populations and thus encroaching human settlements.
2173 The increase in wildlife populations in the area was also attributed to land degradation and
2174 vegetation damage causing shortage of forage for both livestock and wildlife. Nonetheless, other
2175 respondents, though few (5.3%), mentioned that the law did not have any impact on their
2176 livelihoods, opining that nothing has changed in their livelihoods due to the hunting ban law.

2177 In general, the respondents in the household survey believed that “*Government should be*

2178 *responsible for all the compensation for losses and damages caused by wildlife*” as the majority
 2179 (94%) either “agreed” or “strongly agreed” with that statement. Only four percent (3.2% and 0.8%)
 2180 either “disagreed” or “strongly disagreed” to the statement and the remaining two percent could
 2181 not remark over the statement (Table 17). Respondents were also content over wildlife and
 2182 participation in wildlife conservation. Majority of them did not agree to negative statements that
 2183 “*I don’t like wildlife because they destroy my household assets*” and “*I cannot participate in*
 2184 *wildlife conservation because they destroy my household assets*” as 88.7 % and 91.2 % either
 2185 “disagreed” or “strongly disagreed” to the statements, respectively.

2186
 2187 **Table 17: Statements on respondents’ costs of living alongside wildlife**

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
• <i>Government should be responsible for all the compensation for losses and damages caused by wildlife</i>	147 (59.3)	86 (34.7)	5 (2)	8 (3.2)	2 (0.8)
• <i>I do not like wildlife because they destroy my household assets</i>	4 (1.6)	19 (7.7)	5 (2)	135 (54.4)	85 (34.3)
• <i>I cannot participate in wildlife conservation because they destroy my household assets</i>	3 (1.2)	14 (5.6)	5 (2)	129 (52.0)	97 (39.2)

2188 *Note: Percentages are reported in parentheses*
 2189

2190 **6.2.2 Perceived benefits from wildlife conservation**

2191 Most of the respondents (80.2%) during the household survey indicated that they did not
 2192 economically benefit from wildlife conservation initiatives in their area (Figure 25a). About 16.1
 2193 % (40) of the respondents confirmed that they did benefit, and the other 3.6 % said they benefited
 2194 to some extent. Of the 49 respondents who said they benefited or to some extent, the majority
 2195 (57.4%) of them further said they were satisfied with the benefits they got from wildlife

2196 conservation initiatives in their area (Figure 25b). Further, 31.5 % said they were not satisfied with
2197 the benefits they received while about 11.1 % were satisfied to some extent.

2199
2200 **Figure 25: Households' economic benefit from conservation (a) and satisfaction level (b)**

2201
2202 Of the 40 (16.1%) respondents who agreed that their households receive some benefits from
2203 wildlife conservation initiatives, 90 % (36) of them gave examples of the kind of benefits they
2204 receive. Most of the respondents (52.5%) who said they were benefiting from wildlife conservation
2205 initiatives through employment, either them or a member of their household was employed by
2206 either a conservation organisation, tourism company and others. Some (10%) respondents
2207 indicated that they benefited indirectly through scholarships from conservation organisations and
2208 sponsorships for business start-ups for their household members. Further, some of the respondents
2209 (7.5%) benefited through engagements with conservation organisations to raise awareness and
2210 mitigation of impact of wildlife on agriculture. Some (5%) also listed donations of school uniforms
2211 and transportation for school going children as benefits.

2212
2213 Some of the respondents (7.5%) indicated that they benefited through using other resources in their

2214 area such as thatching grasses and fishing for selling. Surprisingly, some of the respondents (10%)
2215 considered compensation for damages caused by wild animals on property as benefits.
2216 Employment seemed to be the most important and common way respondents considered to be
2217 benefiting through from wildlife conservation initiatives. Results from the household survey
2218 indicated that of the 29 (11.7%) respondents who said they are employed, about 48.3 % of them
2219 were employed in the tourism and hospitality sector (Figure 26).

2220

2221

2222 **Figure 26: Categories of household members' sector of employment**

2223

2224 Further, about 24.1 % of the respondents were employed in the wildlife and environment
2225 management sector. The education sector also had a significant number (17.2%) of people
2226 employed, as cooks, guards, and teachers in schools, and the remaining 10.3 % were employed in
2227 different other sectors such as health, rural administration, and others. Of the respondents who said
2228 their households economically benefit from wildlife conservation initiatives, 82.5 % of them also
2229 said they take part in the management of wildlife in their area (Table 18). The majority (80.2%) of
2230 respondents said they were not benefiting from wildlife conservation initiatives, and most (47.7%)

2231 of them said they were not taking part in the management of wildlife in their area compared to
 2232 46.2 % who said they took part.

2233

2234 **Table 18: Participation versus household economic benefit variables**

Questions on household economic benefits		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			Total	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	(%)
<i>Does your household economically benefit from wildlife conservation initiatives?</i>	Benefiting	82.5	17.5	0.0	40	100
	Not benefiting	46.2	47.7	6.1	199	100
	To some extent	44.4	0.0	55.6	9	100
<i>My household benefits from wildlife available in our area</i>	Strongly agree	54.5	40.9	4.5	44	100
	Agree	65.0	23.3	11.7	60	100
	Neutral	60.0	40.0	0.0	10	100
	Disagree	45.8	46.9	7.3	96	100
	Strongly disagree	42.1	55.3	2.6	38	100

2235

2236 On respondents who said they were not benefiting from wildlife conservation initiatives, there was
 2237 no significant difference between those who took part and those who did not, and the other 6.1 %
 2238 said they took part sometimes (Table 18). Also, among respondents who said their households
 2239 economically benefited to some extent from wildlife conservation initiatives, none of them said
 2240 they did not take part in the management of wildlife in their area as some said “yes” (44.4%) they
 2241 did, or they did it “sometimes” (55.6%). Further, a Pearson Chi-Square test indicated a significant
 2242 association between the variables with a value (χ^2) of 53.850 and a p-value of 0.000. The majority
 2243 of respondents who “agreed” and “strongly agreed” to the statement that “*My household benefits*
 2244 *from wildlife available in our area*” also 54.5 % and 65.0 % of them, respectively, agreed that they
 2245 took part in the management of wildlife in their area (Table 18). This is in comparison to 40.9 %
 2246 (Strongly agreed) and 23.3 % (Agreed) of those who said they did not take part in wildlife

2247 management. For those who “disagreed” and “strongly disagreed”, the majority of them, 46.6 %
 2248 and 55.3 %, respectively, said they did not take part in wildlife management, in comparison to 45.8
 2249 % and 42.1 %, respectively, who said they took part. Further, a Pearson Chi-Square test indicated
 2250 no significant association between the two variables, with a value of 14.854 and a p-value of 0.062.
 2251
 2252 In general, respondents during the household survey acknowledged the importance of wildlife and
 2253 its conservation in their area. The respondents supported the statements that “*I believe wildlife*
 2254 *conservation is a strong economic contributor to my community*”, “*Wildlife conservation*
 2255 *diversifies the economy in my community*”, “*Wildlife conservation creates employment*
 2256 *opportunities in my community*”, “*I participate in conservation initiatives if my household is to*
 2257 *benefit directly*”, and “*My community should have a fair share of benefits from wildlife uses (i.e.,*
 2258 *tourism)*” as the majority of them either “agreed” or “strongly agreed” to the statements (Table
 2259 19). On contrary, respondents were also against the statement that “*My household benefits from*
 2260 *wildlife available in our area*” as about 54 % of them “disagreed” and “strongly disagreed” to the
 2261 statement.

2262
 2263 **Table 19: Respondents’ views on the economic contribution of wildlife to livelihoods**

<i>Statement</i>	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
• <i>I believe wildlife conservation is a strong economic contributor to my community</i>	96 (38.7)	94 (37.9)	12 (4.8)	30 (12.1)	16 (6.5)
• <i>Wildlife conservation diversifies the economy in my community</i>	75 (30.2)	115 (46.4)	17 (6.9)	30 (12.1)	11 (4.4)
• <i>Wildlife conservation creates employment opportunities in my community</i>	94 (37.9)	98 (39.5)	16 (6.5)	35 (14.1)	5 (2.0)
• <i>I participate in conservation initiatives if my household is to benefit directly</i>	53 (21.4)	120 (48.4)	16 (6.5)	42 (16.9)	17 (6.9)
• <i>My community should have a fair</i>	139	94 (37.9)	8 (3.2)	3 (1.2)	4 (1.6)

<i>share of benefits from wildlife uses (i.e., tourism)</i>	(56.0)				
•My household benefits from wildlife available in our area	44 (17.7)	60 (24.2)	10 (4.0)	96 (38.7)	38 (15.3)
•I believe wildlife conservation is good for my community's economy	17 (16.8)	36 (35.6)	2 (2.0)	32 (31.7)	14 (13.9)
•I like wildlife conservation because it brings new income to communities	7 (6.9)	38 (37.6)	4 (4.0)	39 (38.6)	13 (12.9)
Total	525 (31.1)	655 (38.7)	85 (5.0)	307 (18.2)	118 (7.0)

2264 *Note: Percentages are reported in parentheses*
2265

2266 **6.2.3 Participation in wildlife conservation as a personal responsibility**

2267 According to results from the household survey, most of the respondents (59.9%) opined that in
2268 their households the youth between ages of 19 and 35, were mostly active in wildlife conservation
2269 issues. Furthermore, about 34.0 % respondents stated that adults (36- to 59-year-olds) actively
2270 participate in wildlife conservation (Figure 27). The remaining 6.1 % of the respondents opined
2271 that the elderly (above 60 years old) members of their households were active in wildlife
2272 conservation.

2275 **Figure 27: Age categories of households' members actively participating in conservation**

2276

2277 Of the respondents who said the elderly actively participated in wildlife conservation issues, 73.3
 2278 % of them agreed that they took part in management of wildlife in their area (Table 20). About 50
 2279 % of adults also said they took part in management of wildlife. The majority of respondents said
 2280 youth were active in wildlife issues, from that, about 51.4 % further said they participated in the
 2281 management of wildlife in their area. Compared to other age categories, a bigger proportion
 2282 (42.6%) of the youth said they did not take part in management of wildlife, compared to 41.7 %
 2283 of adults and 20 % of the elderly.

2284
 2285

Table 20: Participation by age group and contribution opinion

		<i>Do you take part in the management of wildlife in your area?</i>			<i>Total</i>	
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Sometimes (%)	n	%
<i>In your household, which age group actively participate in wildlife conservation issues?</i>	Old age	73.3	20.0	6.7	15	100
	Adults	50.0	41.7	8.3	84	100
	Youth	51.4	42.6	6.1	149	100
<i>I contribute to wildlife conservation decision making in my community</i>	Strongly agree	73.0	21.6	5.4	37	100
	Agree	66.0	25.8	8.2	97	100
	Neutral	57.1	28.6	14.3	7	100
	Disagree	34.7	61.3	4.0	75	100
	Strongly disagree	25.0	65.6	9.4	32	100

2286
 2287 According to answers given by respondents to a Likert's scaled statement that "*I contribute to*
 2288 *wildlife conservation decision making in my community*", the majority of respondents who
 2289 "Strongly agreed" (73.0%) and "Agreed" (66.0%) also said they do take part in the management
 2290 of wildlife in their area (Table 20). Further, about 21.6 % and 25.8 % who "Strongly agreed" and
 2291 "Agreed", respectively, said they did not take part in the management of wildlife. In contrary, the
 2292 majority of respondents who "Disagreed" (61.3%) or "Strongly disagreed" (65.6%) to the
 2293 statement also said they did not take part in management of wildlife. Only 2.8 % (7) of the

2294 respondents did not opine to the statements and about 57.1 % of them said they do take part in
 2295 wildlife management. Further, a Pearson Chi-Square test was run, and it support there is significant
 2296 association between the variables. The test gave a Chi-Square value (χ^2) of 39.131 and a p-value
 2297 of 0.000.

2298
 2299 During household survey, respondents were posed with Likert scaled statements about their
 2300 personal responsibilities towards wildlife conservation. The statement includes “*I have personal*
 2301 *responsibility to participate in wildlife conservation*”, “*I contribute to wildlife conservation*
 2302 *decision making in my community*”, “*I share my opinions with officials regarding wildlife*
 2303 *conservation*”, “*I provide assistance/resources where necessary for wildlife conservation*” and “*I*
 2304 *meet with wildlife officials to discuss conservation issues*”. Accumulatively, the majority of the
 2305 respondents were positive towards the statements as they either “Strongly agreed” or “Agreed” to
 2306 the statements with total of 239 (19.3%) and 516 (41.6%), respectively (Table 21). Also, some
 2307 respondents were negative as they either “Disagreed” or “Strongly disagreed” to the statements
 2308 with total of 298 (24%) and 145 (11.7%), respectively. The total 42 (3.4%) was for respondents
 2309 who were neutral towards the statements.

2310
 2311 **Table 21: Statements on personal responsibilities towards wildlife conservation**

<i>Statement</i>	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
• <i>I have personal responsibility to participate in wildlife conservation</i>	84 (33.9)	132 (53.2)	10 (4.0)	16 (6.5)	6 (2.4)
• <i>I contribute to wildlife conservation decision making in my community</i>	37 (14.9)	97 (39.2)	7 (2.8)	75 (30.2)	32 (12.9)
• <i>I share my opinions with officials regarding wildlife conservation</i>	44 (17.7)	109 (44.0)	10 (4.0)	57 (23.0)	28 (11.3)
• <i>I provide assistance/resources where necessary for wildlife conservation</i>	46 (18.5)	99 (39.9)	8 (3.2)	62 (25.0)	33 (13.3)

•I meet with wildlife officials to discuss conservation issues	28 (11.3)	79 (31.9)	7 (2.8)	88 (35.5)	46 (18.5)
Total	239 (19.3)	516 (41.6)	42 (3.4)	298 (24.0)	145 (11.7)

2312 Note: Percentages are reported in parentheses

2313

2314 For inferential analysis, indexes were generated from the five Likert scale statements variables on
 2315 respondent’s personal responsibilities (Table 21). Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used
 2316 to assess monotonic relationship between the Likert scale variables index and respondents age
 2317 variable. Both variables were continuous. The correlation analysis gave a correlation coefficient
 2318 (ρ) of 0.011. This level of ρ implies that there is *negligible correlation* between age and the way
 2319 a respondent will answer to a combination of Likert scale statements in *Table 21* above. Results
 2320 from the household survey illustrates that there was no significant difference between respondents
 2321 who said they participated and those who did not. Further, respondents advanced reasons for why
 2322 they chose to participate and what they looked at in an initiative before they considered
 2323 participating. Most of the respondents (71%) opined that they considered what could be personal
 2324 benefits before they can decide to take part in a conservation initiative (Figure 28).

2325

2326

2327 **Figure 28: Issues being considered prior participation**

2328
2329 Also, the other important thing that local communities considered before participating was the
2330 importance of the conservation issue at hand (57.3%). Further, about 50.8 % of respondents said
2331 they considered possible implications to their livelihoods for any upcoming or running
2332 conservation initiative or project before they participated. Also, confidence in management
2333 interests (11.7%), confidence in management personalities (7.3%), and other (2%) issues
2334 mentioned, were not of significant impact to choices of community in the study area.

2335

2336 **6.2.4 Value associated with wildlife**

2337 Results from the household survey indicated that local communities realised the value of wildlife
2338 in their area. When quizzed to comment, respondents completely agreed to the statement that
2339 *“Wildlife has an economic value, so people have to take part in its conservation”*. Most
2340 respondents either “Strongly agreed” (44.8%) or “Agreed” (45.6%) to the statement, compared to
2341 only 3.6 % and 2.0 % who either “Disagreed” or “Strongly disagreed” to the statements,
2342 respectively. In general, respondents valued wildlife, as 90.4 % (44.8% and 45.6%) of them were
2343 positive towards the Likert scaled statement. Further, four percent of the respondents did not
2344 comment on the statement.

2345

2346 **6.3 Discussion**

2347 The results indicated that local communities incurred costs associated with living in wildlife
2348 infested areas. Households in the study area also experience costs on their farming activities, and
2349 mostly on cropping. These communities are predominantly rural and poor, and they are likely to
2350 be affected by costs borne from living close to wildlife, whilst obliged to conserve. In such a
2351 situation where livelihoods are threatened, and opportunities missed due to conservation

2352 interventions, conservation objectives suffer (Green et al., 2018), as local communities lose
2353 interest in participating in wildlife conservation. Where costs of conservation are huge, they
2354 normally accrue to few people living alongside wildlife (Green et al., 2018). It was observed in
2355 the study that majority of households lived below the poverty datum line. Previous studies have
2356 illustrated that the poor who occupy undesirable land near wildlife are highly vulnerable to costs
2357 of wildlife damage with minimal options to cope (Karanth et al., 2012). The situation may be
2358 worsened by lack of local support, vacuum in conservation policy intervention, and this implies
2359 minimal cushions against shocks which are mostly unbearable (Green et al., 2018; Kideghesho,
2360 2008).

2361
2362 Crop damage was more pronounced in the study area compared to other threats to farming
2363 activities. It was also reported in studies carried out in other terrestrial ecosystems elsewhere, like
2364 the administrative buffers of national parks in both India and Nepal, that crop damages are more
2365 frequently experienced and pronounced compared to livestock damage and other losses (Karanth
2366 et al., 2012; Karanth & Nepal, 2012). There were mitigation measures put in place by farmers in
2367 the area to protect their crops against raiding by wild animals. The use of noisy materials such as
2368 scrap cans, and metal sheet pieces on fencing were commonly used and perceived to be cheaper
2369 and effective compared to other methods. Elsewhere, in south-east Bangladesh, communities were
2370 also said to be preferring the use of loud noise materials as active deterrent methods against
2371 elephants (Sarker & Røskaft, 2011).

2372
2373 Deterrent methods, particularly for elephants in crop fields, are mostly the same in Asia and Africa,
2374 and equally inadequate to mitigate effects of conflict between local communities and elephants
2375 (O'Connell-Rodwell, Rodwell, Rice, & Hart, 2000; Sarker & Røskaft, 2011). These shortfalls in

2376 efforts of households to protect their main source of livelihood demoralises them and halts their
2377 chances of self-organising as local communities to conserve wildlife, particularly problem animals.
2378 As a policy measure, the Government of Botswana introduced compensation for wildlife damages
2379 to offset costs incurred by households, help mitigate effects and reduce wildlife crimes (Kgathi,
2380 Mmopelwa, Mashabe, & Mosepele, 2012). Earlier studies found that households in the Okavango
2381 Delta rely on the compensation programme, together with other coping strategies in alleviating
2382 impacts on agricultural production setbacks caused by wildlife (Kolawole et al., 2016).

2383
2384 This study revealed that less than half of the households in the study area received compensation
2385 amid damages on crops and livestock by wildlife. Earlier studies in the Okavango Delta have
2386 specified that local communities do not report incidences when they are aware that they will not
2387 attract compensation, therefore the number of cases reported and the amount of compensation
2388 rolled out by government do not reflect the actual damages caused by wildlife on agricultural
2389 production (Kgathi et al., 2012; Noga, Kolawole, Thakadu, & Masunga, 2017; Noga et al., 2018).
2390 Results from a study carried out by Karanth et al. (2012) in central India are consistent with the
2391 findings of this study, that the majority of local communities experience damages to farm
2392 properties by wildlife, most report the loss to authority, and few receive compensation. This reveals
2393 the magnitude of costs experienced by local communities living alongside wildlife, and the very
2394 little support reaching them to mitigate losses (Zanamwe, Gandiwa, Muboko, Kupika, &
2395 Mukamuri, 2018).

2396
2397 The rate at which local communities incur cost might put them in a puzzling situation, of whether
2398 to conserve or destroy. Also, findings of this study indicate that for households who received
2399 compensation, most were not satisfied. This could be a precursor, not only for local communities'

2400 poor participation in wildlife conservation, but also for increasing wildlife conflict and crime
2401 (Karanth et al., 2012). In Sri Lanka for example, it was easier, and thrilling, for local communities
2402 to either kill or injure elephants whenever they damage their crops because they considered the
2403 compensation unsatisfactory (Singh, Sankaran, Mander, & Worah, 2000: Case 19). Well
2404 administered and satisfactory compensation scheme is vital in advancing wildlife conservation
2405 objectives, as it helps in incentivising local communities to actively participate in conservation
2406 and mitigate costs of damage, thus promoting sustainable livelihoods.

2407
2408 Restrictions and regulations put in place, mainly for conservation purposes, was also mentioned in
2409 this study as a limitation to how local communities can use resources. Such limitations do not only
2410 deny local communities access, but also power to rightfully manage and sustainably use the
2411 resources (Mogende & Ramutsindela, 2020; Pathak & Kothari, 1998). This could possibly affect
2412 their endeavours to optimally profit, or basically harvest for livelihood purposes (Noe &
2413 Kangalawe, 2016). Where conservation objectives dictate that local communities have little or no
2414 access to natural resources, it does not necessarily lead to good biodiversity conservation outcomes
2415 (Singh et al., 2000; Sinha & Singh, 2011), particularly in terrestrial ecosystems like the Okavango
2416 Delta. Further, Singh et al., (2000) opined that local communities are equally susceptible, like
2417 central governments, to over exploit and destruct resources upon assuming power and control over
2418 resources. Fortunately, the proceeds could revolve around the local poor and could be vital in
2419 uplifting livelihoods standards of the rural majority (Singh et al., 2000).

2420
2421 On the hunting ban, which the government of Botswana introduced as a conservation strategy, to
2422 curb the then reported rapidly declining wildlife populations in the area, results of this study
2423 indicates that it has adversely impacted households' livelihood in the area. The decision to

2424 introduce the ban was more centralised (Mogende & Ramutsindela, 2020), and lacked community
2425 involvement from inception (Mbaiwa, 2018). Such conservation initiatives mostly negatively
2426 impact local communities, and are unsustainable and less effective (Zanamwe et al., 2018). Several
2427 earlier studies outlined that prior to the introduction of the hunting ban, in 2014, poor households
2428 were benefiting from hunting, as they had free meat, employment in hunting safari companies and
2429 collective proceeds through CBOs (Blackie, 2019; Mbaiwa, 2018).

2430
2431 Generally, local communities prefer a situation where there is balance between conservation
2432 objectives and households livelihood needs (Karanth & Nepal, 2012). Consistent with other
2433 previous studies, results of this study indicate that benefits derived by local communities from
2434 wildlife conservation were outweighed by costs experienced. On their analysis, on “Who pays for
2435 wildlife conservation in Tanzania and who benefits?”, Kideghesho (2008) indicates that the
2436 central government and conservation agencies highly benefit from wildlife whereas local
2437 communities endure costs the most. The same applies to a particular group of resettled farmers in
2438 Namibia who did not have any user rights and benefits from wildlife whereas they continuously
2439 lost their livestock to predators (Rust & Marker, 2013). Also, it was found out that extending
2440 benefits to local communities living near wildlife protected areas in Asia could help offset huge
2441 losses experienced by poor and resource dependent households (Karanth & Nepal, 2012; Pettigrew
2442 et al., 2012; Sinha & Singh, 2011). Without addressing differences between benefits and costs,
2443 local community participation in wildlife conservation cannot be achieved.

2444
2445 Local communities’ efforts in participating in management of resources around them is related to
2446 the benefits and satisfaction they get from the resources (Zanamwe et al., 2018). Choices of local
2447 communities resonates around what was of interest to their livelihoods before what could be their

2448 personal responsibility. Results of this study further indicated that most people whose household
2449 needs were met through proceeds from wildlife conservation initiatives, did not take part in the
2450 management of wildlife in their area. Regrettably, those who benefited were very few. Singh et al.
2451 (2000) observed that “self-interest” is vital as it serves as motivation of local communities to
2452 conserve. Communities, with their interests served, are pivotal in effecting decentralised, and
2453 inclusive resource governance and bringing about meaningful conservation outcomes through
2454 participation (Agrawal & Gibson, 1999). The question may be asked, of, what are the interests of
2455 local communities? The answer revolves around the kind of benefits attached to conservation,
2456 either in form of user rights, resource tenure, and direct or indirect economic benefits.

2457
2458 Also, the administrative processes of wildlife conservation are of interest to local communities.
2459 For example, it was earlier found that people who were benefiting through employment, were not
2460 satisfied with the CBNRM processes in Sankuyo village, northern Botswana (Boggs, 2000). Like
2461 in many other African countries, CBNRM initiatives are a wheel in fostering local community
2462 participation and beneficiation from resources around (Musavengane & Simatele, 2016;
2463 O’Connell-Rodwell et al., 2000; Poteete, 2009; Sarker & Røskaft, 2011). The magnitude of losses
2464 experienced by local communities due to damage to property by wildlife counters the earlier
2465 reported successes of CBNRM initiatives (Blackie, 2019).

2466
2467 This study stems from a collective action approach, which is social capital, as illustrated in the
2468 conceptual framework in Chapter Two, where local communities organise themselves to embark
2469 on a common goal. In such an instance, local communities as both individuals and groups or
2470 society will better understand both management processes and benefits of conserving wildlife.
2471 Private benefits received by individuals for their contribution are an incentive for collective action

2472 activities (Ntuli & Muchapondwa, 2018). Self-organising among local communities is sometimes
2473 done to sustainably use or conserve resources as a common responsibility (Ntuli & Muchapondwa,
2474 2018). The voluntary involvement of people to pursue activities of common interest is “social
2475 capital”. According to Boggs (2000), communities in the Okavango Delta (case of Sankuyo
2476 community) were found to be not appreciative to the importance of actively participating in
2477 wildlife management, supposedly due to culturally dictated responsibilities and free-rider
2478 mentality. But this might be due to other factors. The inability or lack of capacity of communities
2479 to solve a common problem is referred to as “common action problem” (Ntuli & Muchapondwa,
2480 2018).

2481
2482 Results of this study indicates that local communities recognise the economic value of wildlife in
2483 their area and the importance to conserve. In the province of Alberta, Canada, where wildlife was
2484 valued using economic methods, it was found out that wildlife benefits were well in the interests
2485 of the society (Adamowiczi, Asafu-Adjaye, Boxall, & Phillipisi, 1991). The value of wildlife was
2486 found by translating annual benefits into present asset value. According to Child & Bergstrøm
2487 (2002), most wildlife values can be quantified economically, therefore being easier to be allocated
2488 to people as groups rather than individuals. When there is conflict in resource user rights or tenure,
2489 the value of such resource becomes of insignificance to local communities. In such a case, local
2490 communities residing alongside a resource will feel disenfranchised and have no sense of
2491 responsibly to conserve (Boggs, 2000).

2492 **6.4 Conclusion**

2493 It is evident from this chapter that local communities living alongside wildlife in the Greater
2494 Seronga Area suffer costs in pursuit of livelihoods compared to benefits gained. This can be
2495 generalised to other identical communities around the Okavango Delta who live within similar
2496 conditions. Where costs surpass benefits, local communities are less inclined to participate in the
2497 conservation of a resource even if they have the ability and opportunity to do so. Overwhelming
2498 costs demoralise local communities, who highly need some motivation to participate in resource
2499 management for better conservation outputs. To help improve living standards of communities
2500 near wildlife areas, who experience opportunity costs due to land use regulations, governments
2501 should promote more decentralised management of resources. With more decentralised resource
2502 management processes, local communities will be able to enjoy access, user rights, tenure, and
2503 power over the resources. When local communities have the responsibility over resources, they
2504 are able to link the benefits to the same resource, therefore be obliged to conserve.

2505 **CHAPTER 7**

2506 **DRIVERS OF COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN WILDLIFE CONSERVATION IN THE GREATER**
2507 **SERONGA AREA OF THE OKAVANGO DELTA, BOTSWANA: SYNTHESIS AND SUGGESTIONS**

2508 **7.1 Synthesis**

2509 Communities living alongside wildlife meet challenges in their endeavours to meet their livelihood
2510 needs. The challenges come as a result of community interaction with wildlife without defined
2511 interdependence approach and conflict mitigation. Community participation in conservation is
2512 fundamental for sustainability of resources use and rural development. Management decisions on
2513 coexistence of humans and wildlife within the Okavango Delta ecosystem are key to biodiversity
2514 conservation and sustainable development. There is a need to strike a balance between wildlife
2515 conservation and sustenance of rural livelihoods in order to achieve mutual benefit to both
2516 biodiversity and local communities (Adams & Hutton, 2007; Chan et al., 2020; Noga et al., 2018).
2517 A good understanding of the driving factors impacting on community participation in wildlife
2518 conservation is important for developing appropriate policies for managing the now precarious co-
2519 existence of wildlife and local communities in the Okavango Delta. Therefore, the thesis analysed
2520 the drivers of community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives in the Greater Seronga
2521 Area of the Okavango Delta, Botswana. Specifically, the thesis: a) assessed socio-cultural factors
2522 influencing local community participation in wildlife conservation initiatives, b) analysed the
2523 influence of management strategies on local community participation in wildlife conservation
2524 initiatives, and c) assessed the influence of household economic trade-offs on local community
2525 participation in wildlife conservation initiatives.

2526

2527 This thesis was informed by the integrative Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) model of
2528 community participation and the Social-Ecological systems (SES) framework. The framework
2529 guided the conceptualisation of factors of motivation, opportunity, and ability and how they
2530 influenced community participation in management of wildlife. The factors are crucial in enforcing
2531 active participation of local communities in management processes, particularly of wildlife in this
2532 case. The thesis employed a cross-sectional passive-analytical mixed-methods approach. Both
2533 qualitative and quantitative data was collected from randomly selected household heads using
2534 household survey, and purposively identified key informants through the villages of Seronga,
2535 Gunotsoga, Eretsha, Beetsha and Gudigwa. Quantitative techniques including Spearman's rho
2536 correlation coefficient test and Pearson Chi-Square test, and qualitative analysis technique
2537 including thematic analysis were used to find the relationship between community socio-cultural,
2538 administrative, and economic factors influencing local community participation in wildlife
2539 conservation within the study area.

2540
2541 **7.1.1 The influence of socio-cultural factors on local community participation in**
2542 **wildlife conservation**

2543 Every community will at any point in time, regardless of their social, cultural, economic, and
2544 legislative conditions, have rationale for their form of participation in a project. The first specific
2545 objective which sought to assess socio-cultural factors influencing local community participation
2546 in wildlife conservation was aligned to the component of ability as discussed in the MOA model
2547 of community participation. Results in Chapter 4 of this thesis illustrated that local communities
2548 in the study area had limited ability or capacity, as they were mostly unskilled and uninformed, to
2549 participate in wildlife conservation. Therefore, this led to low awareness on how to embark on
2550 management processes even when opportunities existed and there was motivation or enjoying

2551 certain benefits. In such a case, inclusive management processes might become undesirable
2552 because of limited ability of targeted communities. In addition to ability, open opportunities for
2553 involvement of local communities in decision making and direct benefits are crucial for achieving
2554 successful community conservation (Boggs, 2000). Natural resources management institutions and
2555 organisations need to align and develop necessary social skills, improve awareness and
2556 communication in order to achieve their objectives. Local communities are likely to support and
2557 participate in initiatives when they are well capacitated and informed on formal management
2558 process, agenda and expected outcomes.

2559

2560 **7.1.2 Management strategies and local community participation in wildlife** 2561 **conservation**

2562
2563 The second specific objective explored the kind of opportunity local communities had to
2564 participate in wildlife conservation and therefore analysed the influence of formal management
2565 strategies on local community participation in wildlife conservation. Opportunity in this thesis has
2566 been defined as the inclusiveness of participation processes by facilitating community involvement
2567 in decision-making. The inclusiveness of management strategies involves the availability of a clear
2568 channel of communication between the general community members and the authorities
2569 responsible for formulating and implementing management decisions (Jepson et al., 2013). The
2570 results, in Chapter 5 demonstrated that there were no localised institutions or processes in form of
2571 policy or legislative instruments supporting inclusive natural resource management. Nonetheless,
2572 this centralised format overshadowed available social and cultural norms for collective
2573 management like the Kgotla and Kgosi system as would the SES framework predict. This
2574 consequently implies that local communities do not have ownership and decision-making rights
2575 over resources in their area.

2576

2577 Community inclusive management strategies involves a complete sequence of initiation,
2578 processing, implementation, and monitoring of management decisions on sustainable use of
2579 wildlife. Even so, Cassidy (2020) established that local institutions such as the Kgotla and the
2580 VDCs have over time acquired bargaining power for management of resources and the CBNRM
2581 has somehow strengthened their robustness. Management policies, like the CBNRM policy, and
2582 other strategies in place, do not have instruments aiming the present state and site-specific socio-
2583 economic circumstances in order to genuinely accommodate local communities. The available
2584 platforms of stakeholder engagement were thus detached from and marginally influenced
2585 community participation, particularly in wildlife conservation. This violates one of the design
2586 principles building up to the robustness of the SES framework that, “most individuals affected by
2587 harvesting and protection rules are included in the group who can modify these rules” (Anderies
2588 et al., 2004).

2589

2590 Therefore, the management of wildlife in the Greater Seronga Area was mainly centralised and
2591 marginally involving users of the resource, being local communities, in wildlife conservation
2592 decision-making processes. Targeting communities in small groups, like villages, through their
2593 local institutions and their self-organisations would widen the community inclusiveness
2594 mechanism and acceptance of conservation strategies, thus improving biodiversity outcomes.
2595 Generally, developing countries, Botswana inclusive, do not prioritise the formulation of area-
2596 specific policies and local administration of resources, and the central governments plays a critical
2597 role in management of wildlife (Blackie, 2019; Ngwira, Kolawole, & Mbaiwa, 2013). Even though
2598 governments in many African states have centralised decision-making processes over sustainable

2599 resource use, they also experience deficiency in economic and institutional capacity to effectively
2600 serve rural communities living alongside wildlife (Ngwira et al., 2013).

2601

2602 **7.1.3 Effect of household economic trade-offs on local community participation in** 2603 **wildlife conservation**

2604 Lastly, the third specific objective explored the motivation aspect of the MOA model of
2605 community participation by assessing the influence of household economic trade-offs on local
2606 community participation in wildlife conservation. This thesis underscored the aspect of motivation
2607 as an important driving factor of community's decision to participate in wildlife conservation. It
2608 supported assertions by Jepson et al. (2013) that motivation affects the intensity and direction of
2609 the behaviour of communities to participate in decision-making processes. The results
2610 demonstrated that participation in decision making processes is influenced by communities'
2611 perceived benefits of the initiative and the level and way by which it is expected to affect
2612 livelihoods. In illustrating the usefulness of the SES framework, Ostrom (2009) posed a question
2613 of "when will the users of a resource invest time and energy to avert a tragedy of the commons?"
2614 This thesis borrowed from the theoretical answer in analysing effects of household, as users,
2615 economic trade-offs, as motivation, in driving the users to self-organise and manage a common
2616 resource for its sustainability and self-gain. The answer by Ostrom (2009) also revolved around,
2617 as per the findings of this thesis, the margin between household benefits and costs, that if expected
2618 benefits overweigh the perceived costs then users are more likely self-organise for resource
2619 management purposes.

2620

2621 The results also indicated that the kind of benefits, such as tourism employment, sponsorships, and
2622 donations, enjoyed by local communities living alongside wildlife in the Greater Seronga Area

2623 significantly influence their participation behaviour. Local communities incurred some costs such
2624 as crop damages and livestock predation which surpassed benefits thus demoralising local
2625 communities who are able and had opportunity to participate in wildlife conservation. Low
2626 proportions (16.1%) of households benefited and whereas high proportions experienced costs on
2627 either crop damage (68.5%) or livestock predation (35.5%). Findings of this thesis demonstrated
2628 a significant association between benefits and participation. Where there were more costs accruing
2629 to local communities who are usually marginalised and poor, any kind of benefits become
2630 insignificant (Green et al., 2018). Those communities become less inclined to actively participate
2631 in wildlife conservation even if they had the ability and opportunity to do so (Karanth & Nepal,
2632 2012).

2633
2634 This thesis analysed how community socio-economic, cultural, and administrative and individuals'
2635 personal conditions may stimulate their participation behaviour, and also emphasising the
2636 importance of participatory approaches in wildlife conservation. This cannot be done without
2637 recognising the importance of collective action on wildlife conservation (Ntuli & Muchapondwa,
2638 2018; Ostrom, 2007). Therefore, the theoretical underpinnings stemmed from the community
2639 social bargaining influence on social relations and the interaction processes of those communities.
2640 Decentralising the management of natural resources to local communities is accepted for their
2641 active participation, where people are involved, not as distinct individuals, but as a collective
2642 (Agarwal, 2001). Where there is no social capital and communities fail to communicate and
2643 organise themselves into formally recognised groups, both livelihoods and conservation outcomes
2644 fail (Ntuli & Muchapondwa, 2018; Ostrom, 2009).

2645

2646 **7.2 Key suggestions**

2647 The ideal form of participation for the Greater Seronga Area is the interactive rather than the
2648 observed consultative participation mainly due to several driving factors as described in this thesis.
2649 Interactive participation involves members of a community equally having a chance to voice and
2650 influence decisions in their local group settings (Agarwal, 2001). Interactive participation
2651 empowers local communities to become party to important management discussions and decisions
2652 on wildlife conservation. To achieve that, several aspects driving community participation will
2653 need consideration, therefore this thesis suggests the following:

2654 a) There is need for the government to continue support the organisation of locals into formal
2655 institutions to improve their input and engagement in development of wildlife conservation
2656 initiatives. Collectively well organised local communities with a common goal and interest
2657 are better placed to sustainably manage resources in their area compared to outsiders.
2658

2659 b) Stakeholders concerned with wildlife conservation need to prioritise capacity building
2660 within their target populations more especially marginalised groups in rural areas like the
2661 Greater Seronga Area. Equipping locals with skills and knowledge of basic formal
2662 processes is essential for building confidence amongst local communities to engage in
2663 boundless activities like wildlife conservation. Also, stakeholders should strive to improve
2664 local community's access to information and communication to better their awareness on
2665 issues of wildlife management and decision making.
2666

2667 c) Local communities at household level need to be supported to use wildlife and other
2668 resources for entrepreneurship purposes, particularly non-consumptive tourism for them to
2669 realise direct benefits from the resources. This could help improve the sense of ownership
2670

2671 over resources among local communities and reduce dependence on outsider investors for
2672 employment opportunities and donations. Direct benefits are critical in motivating
2673 communities to conserve a resource.

2674

2675 **7.3 Future work**

2676 a) It will be of interest to study how land use laws and regulations impact on local
2677 communities' resilience over wildlife conflict and how they participate in conservation.

2678

2679 b) Future research should be done to create a practical framework on how main factors
2680 influencing community participation can be harnessed to achieve appropriate form of
2681 participation for particular projected outcomes.

2682

2683 c) Further, a study assessing possible participation structures and methods for possible
2684 participatory action should be done, to help guide in implementation of future strategies.

2685

2686 **7.4 Limitations of the study**

2687 a) The study was cross-sectional and therefore data was collected once from each subject. The
2688 data collection process took place at the peak of the Covid-19 pandemic, and it was
2689 imperative that the research team follow all the safety protocols to protect the participants.

2690 More time was invested in the debriefing of the respondents on the mandate and the scope
2691 of the study to avoid possible effects the pandemic era could have had on the opinions of a
2692 lot of participants over their livelihoods and economic activities and possible deviation of
2693 attention from the subject of interest which is participation in conservation. Many people in
2694 the area lost their jobs in the tourism sector and some businesses were closed. A lot of

2695 participants based their views around the pandemic situation and the uncertainty it brought
2696 to their livelihoods and future.

2697
2698 b) It was also important to invest in gaining public trust and confidence before resuming the
2699 interviews as the data collection was conducted at a time where investigations by security
2700 agents surrounding the reports of mass dying of elephants in the Greater Seronga Area was
2701 ongoing. About more than 350 elephants were sighted dead between March and June 2020
2702 in the area. Finding out the cause of death was eminent, and communities felt they were
2703 being victimized in the process because of presence and interrogation by security agents
2704 and some researchers. Even though publications and commentary ruled out the possibility
2705 of poisoning and poaching (Azeem, Bengis, Van Aarde, & Bastos, 2020), it was obvious
2706 that communities would be reluctant and claim lack of knowledge about any wildlife
2707 conservation issues to avoid further discussions or even being summoned to witness about
2708 the dying of elephants. More efforts were put on guaranteeing participants in household
2709 survey confidentiality and protection of information and disclosing their identity to third
2710 parties.

2711
2712 c) During data collection, respondents diverted from the interview to talking with anger about
2713 the damage caused by elephants in their fields. This was so because of the persistent and
2714 high human-wildlife conflict more especially one caused by elephants in the area which
2715 could lead to lack of tolerance from the communities particularly on issues of wildlife
2716 conservation as the data collection process was done just two months from the harvesting
2717 period. Therefore, the researcher and assistant spent more time explaining the purpose of
2718 the study in details.

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